

**BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS**

**STUDIES ON THE VARIABILITY OF MESOSPHERE-LOWER
THERMOSPHERE DYNAMICS OVER LOW-LATITUDE USING LONG-
TERM SABER OBSERVATIONS**

**BY
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THERMOSPHERE DYNAMICS OVER LOW-LATITUDE USING LONG-
TERM SABER OBSERVATIONS

By
Chalachew Lingerew

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Declaration

Chalachew Lingerew Bizuneh, I declare that this Dissertation entitled “Studies on the Variability of Mesosphere-Lower-Thermosphere Dynamics over Low-Latitude Using Long-term SABER Observations” and the research works presented in it all belongs my own original works under the supervision of Dr. Jaya Prakash Raju. I confirm that:

- I have fully acknowledged and referenced the ideas and work of others.
- This dissertation has not been submitted for any other degree or qualification.
- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.

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**Bahir Dar University College of Science Department of Physics Approval of
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Dedication

to

My mom, Siraye Bable.

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Sincerely Yours
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Abstract

This dissertation deals about the Earth's Mesosphere-Lower Thermosphere (MLT) region over the low latitude 3-15⁰ N and its characteristics based on the atmospheric field parameters temperature, ozone and other proxy data. MLT is a highly turbulent and transitional dynamic regions since due to atmospheric waves (gravity, tidal and planetary wave) from the lower atmosphere and radiation energy from the upper atmosphere. Therefore, studies on the MLT dynamics and their variabilities have been carried out for a better understanding as follows.

Chapter 4 investigates the characterization and the dynamics of atmospheric variability based on MLT temperature and ozone oscillations, and found their impacts using the proxy data during 2005-2020. A wavelet analysis technique has been used to identify the dominant oscillations SAO, AO, QBO, ENSO, and SCO. Further using a Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR) technique the impacts of natural drivers F10.7, ENSO, and QBO based on the proxy data of F10.7, Nino 3.4, and zonal wind index respectively. Among the natural drivers (F10.7, ENSO, QBO), solar radio flux (F10.7), influences the temperatures of lower MLT region negatively and it influences positively above 80 km up to 2.6 K, while ozone responds with a constant negative value of -0.12ppmv up to 80 km, and it influences positively above 80km by 0.7 ppmv. At 80 km, the temperature and ozone respond in phase to all natural influences (F10.7, ENSO, and QBO), and are out of phase below and above 80 km. Both the temperature and the ozone reveals a cooling trends (0.85 K/decade and 0.12 ppmv/decade) in the lower MLT and followed by warming trends (1.25 K/decade and 0.27 ppmv/decade) at the upper MLT (85-100 km). In general, the impact of natural drivers on MLT region temperature is stronger than ozone.

Chapter 5 deals the upper and lower inversion Phenomenon over MLT region and their causatives. Phenomenon of inversion in the MLT region is a great scientific interest. Since, their formation mechanisms are poorly understood. Therefore, based on the long-term SABER temperature during 2005-2020 the upper and lower inversions with their causative gravity waves are investigated. The frequency of occurrence rates for lower (below 20%) and for upper inversions (below 40%) are identified, which the upper inversion is dominance over the lower inversion. The upper inversion exists in the height range of 78-91 km with inversion amplitude of ~20-80 k and thickness of ~3-12 km, whereas lower inversion is confined in the height range of 70-80 km with inversion amplitude of ~10-60 k and thickness of ~4-10 km. The gravity wave indicator potential energy depicts high energy (below 100J/kg) at upper MLT region (90 & 85

km) compared to lower MLT region (75 & 70 km) with below 50J/kg. The stability criteria from Brunt-Vaisala frequency (N^2) indicates that upper MLT region (90 & 85 km) possess highly instability (very low values) relative to the lower MLT region (75 & 70 km), which supports the observation of high frequent occurrence of upper inversion compare to lower inversion. The results leads the conclusion that, high amount of gravity wave potential energy is a consequence to high instability in the upper inversion relative to the lower inversion.

Chapter 6 devise the state of art NN-MLT model and its performance with empirical model NRLMSISE2-0. The models are the primary tools of the upper atmosphere research community. Hence, the neural network based efficient regional NN-MLT model development and their prediction is carried out for further understanding the MLT dynamics using long-term SABER temperature observations in chapter 6. Therefore, the necessity for studies focused on the MLT region cannot be overstated, as they are essential for developing reliable and effective models to makes continuous monitoring of these challenging that meet the accuracy requirements of satellite-based observations. The data set during 2006-2020 was split, with 90% used for training and the remaining 10% allocated for prediction. While, the model's validation was tested with two other partitions 80(20) & 70(30). The 90(10) partition of high correlation coefficient (R), low standard deviation (σ), and low root mean square error (RMSE) of the model demonstrated its good performance. The statistical metrics (R , RMSE, mean, and σ) of the SABER observations at three altitude levels (60, 75, & 90 km), aligns closely with the NN-MLT model and empirical (NRLMSISE2-0) model. The NN-MLT model displays a high R (0.74) and low RMSE (4.35 K) at 60 km, indicating its effective performance compared to the other two heights of 75 & 90 km. The NN-MLT model's prediction of MLT temperature variability agree well with the SABER data at all altitudes, particularly at 60 km. whereas the NN-MLT model accurately captures the seasonal variations of MLT temperature, the analysis leads us to the conclusion that it consistently outperforms the empirical model and aligns closely with observations.

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- Lingerew, C., Jaya Prakash Raju, U., & Guimarães Santos, C. A. (2023). NN-MLT model prediction for low-latitude region based on neural network and long-term SABER observations. *Earth and Space Science*, *10*, e2023EA002930. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023EA002930>.
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Abbreviations

ANN	Artificial neural network
AO	Annual oscillation
cENSO	Cold El Nino-Southern Oscillation
CIRA	COSPAR International Reference Atmosphere
CWT	Continuous wavelet transform
DTM	Drag temperature model
ENSO	El Nino-Southern Oscillation
EUV	Extreme ultraviolet
GWPS	Global Wavelet Power Spectrum
GWs	Gravity waves
IR	Infrared radiation
KW	kelvin waves
LEO	Low-Earth orbit
LS	Least squares
MAPE	Mean absolute percentage error
MAE	Mean absolute error
MET	Marshall Engineering Thermosphere
MILs	Mesospheric inversion layers
MLR	Multivariate linear regression
MLS	Microwave Limb Sounder
MLT	Mesosphere and lower thermosphere
MSIS	Mass spectrometric inhomogeneous scattering
MTI	Mesospheric temperature inversion
MWF	Morlet wavelet function
OVMR	Ozone volume mixing ratio
PWs	Planetary waves
QBO	Quasi-Biannual oscillations
RMSE	Root mean square error
SABER	Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry
SAO	Semiannual oscillations

SC	Solar cycle
SD	Standard deviations
SFU	Solar flux units
SST	Sea surface temperature
TIMED	Thermosphere Ionosphere Mesosphere Energetics and Dynamics
UT	Universal time
WACCM	Whole-atmosphere community climate model
wENSO	Warm El Nio phase of Southern Oscillation
WPS	Wavelet power spectral

CHAPTER ONE

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the MLT Region

The earth's atmosphere is host to various atmospheric phenomena and a natural laboratory that enables a vast array of physical, chemical, and dynamic processes. In recent decades, many interesting studies have been carried out in different regions of the Earth's atmosphere through various theoretical and observational studies. The Earth's atmosphere is so vital to the existence of life on Earth, it absorbs high-energy ultraviolet and X-ray radiation from the upper atmosphere before reaching the Earth's surface. This neutral atmospheric thermal structure according to vertical distributions of temperature with altitude is divided into four regions: the troposphere (ground surface to 15 km), stratosphere (15-50 km), mesosphere (50-90 km), and thermosphere (90-400 km).

Extensive studies in the troposphere and stratosphere have been conducted to examine the most important species (e.g., ozone, water vapor, etc.) as well as chemical and dynamical processes in relation to the mesosphere and lower thermosphere regions. The Mesosphere-Lower Thermosphere (MLT, 60 km to 100 km) is the most complex and least understood dynamic region of the Earth's atmosphere due to the scarcity of continuous observations. The mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) region, is a sensitive and dynamic region of the Earth's atmosphere that interacts with the lower and upper atmospheric systems. MLT region is very decisive for attaining notions of atmospheric waves or oscillations, which govern atmospheric dynamics. The unique features of this region distinguish the MLT from other atmospheric layers ([Smith, 2012](#)), including the coldest naturally occurring temperatures. The MLT region has been investigated for decades using ground (Lidar and Radar) and rocketsonde data ([Keckhut et al., 1995](#); [She et al., 2009](#)). These observations during the last decade have enhanced our understanding of the MLT region dynamics, even with limitations hampered by good equipment. Rocket soundings are limited because they are site-specific and only provide a snapshot of atmospheric parameters. Lidar captures data from a small area because its wavelength does not allow it to detect things further from its location (surroundings) and is unable to perform properly in severe weather circumstances such as heavy rain, clouds, snow, and fog in addition to

spatial constraints. As a result, both the spatial (regional) and temporal (periodic) observations conducted for investigations are limited. Hence Satellite observations supplement ground-based observations by providing global coverage with high resolution. Now and then various researchers have undertaken intermittent investigations on the middle and upper atmospheric regions based on satellite data to understand the dynamics caused by atmospheric oscillations and waves (e.g., [Das, 2021](#); [She et al., 2019](#)), and these studies are still ongoing. TIMED/SABER observations, among other satellites, provide a long period of global data with good spatial and temporal resolutions, assisting in the analysis of MLT dynamics ([Bizuneh et al., 2022](#); [Gan et al., 2012, 2014, 2017](#); [Nath and Sridharan, 2014](#); [Xu et al., 2007](#)).

Most notably, the MLT's distinct characteristics are due to prevailing natural oscillations (semiannual oscillation-SAO, annual oscillation-AO, quasi-biannual oscillation-QBO, ElNio-Southern Oscillation-ENSO, and solar radio flux-F10.7) contribute to the atmospheric dynamics of thermal structure, variability, and circulation. Seasonal oscillations (SAO and AO) are well-known atmospheric influences in the equatorial regions, and they are significant causes of intra-annual changes ([Yue et al., 2019](#); [Ern et al., 2015](#)). In addition to seasonal oscillations, natural factors like QBO, ENSO, and SC have become critical for precisely understanding long-term fluctuations and trends in middle atmospheric dynamics ([Kishore et al., 2014](#); [Li et al., 2013](#)). Past studies have focused on the middle and upper atmospheric regions affected by natural oscillations at the middle and high latitudes (e.g., [Das, 2021](#); [She et al., 2019](#)); other researchers have also studied its effects in the lower atmosphere at the middle and high latitudes. Most among them studied, the influence of QBO and ENSO on middle atmospheric temperature variability ([Li et al., 2008](#); [Li et al., 2013](#); [Domeisen et al., 2019](#)) and ozone variability ([Olsen et al. 2019](#)). The F10.7 solar activity, in addition to the QBO and ENSO Oscillations, is a substantial source of variability in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) region ([Bordi et al., 2015](#); [Fadnavis et al., 2012](#); [Beig et al., 2008](#); [Offer Mann et al., 2008](#)).

To understand the MLT dynamics, additional investigations, including the influence of atmospheric waves such as tidal waves, planetary waves, and gravity waves, as causative to the MLT inversion phenomena, are required in addition to the influence of natural oscillations. Understanding MIL phenomena is important under the influence of atmospheric waves for the understanding of middle and upper atmosphere dynamics for two primary reasons: stability and energy transfer. During propagation, these waves particularly gravity waves deposit their energy

in the MLT region when the waves are at saturation level in breaking processes (Fritts; Alexander, 2003). Thus, the wave features strongly shape the dynamic state of the MLT region. These waves in MLT dynamics serve as a transition zone between the lower atmosphere, heavily influenced by anthropogenic (Beig, 2011; Beig et al., 2003) and atmospheric wave activity (Nicolls et al., 2014; Bishop et al., 2006), and the upper atmosphere, subject to significant solar activity and radiative forcing. Mesospheric inversion layers (MILs) are a common phenomenon that appeared in the temperature profiles of the MLT region. Temperature inversions have been ubiquitous in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere for decades and have been extensively studied across geographic regions. Their research continues to be of great importance in understanding the thermal structure, variability, dynamic energy, and momentum budgets of the MLT regions. Studies have mostly focused on the generation of atmospheric wave processes associated with MILs (Gan et al., 2012; Walterscheid and Hickey, 2009) and the generation of turbulence associated with MILs (Collins et al., 2011; Szweczyk et al., 2013) in the MLT dynamics. All these inversion studies were conducted to understand their underlying causal mechanisms (Fritts, 2018; Collins et al., 2014; Sridharan et al., 2008; Ramesh et al., 2013; Ramesh and Sridharan, 2012; Ramesh et al., 2012; et al., 2014; Ramesh et al., 2017).

Furthermore, a thorough understanding of the properties of the MLT region is necessary to develop an effective model. Various scientific and operational models have been developed to understand the dynamics of MLT variability, including the Jacchia series model, the drag temperature model (DTM), and the mass spectrometric inhomogeneous scattering (MSIS) model (Hedin, 1987, 1991; Hedin et al., 1977; Reber and Hays, 1973). The Jacchia-71 model, later updated to the COSPAR International Reference Atmosphere (CIRA-72), is an empirical model that has been used to measure the temperature and density of the MLT region since the early 1960s. Since the early 1970s, Alan Hedin and others have created a new density model called MSIS, which is a popular choice for atmospheric modeling in the scientific community. Various researchers have employed the MSIS family of models (MSISE-86, MSISE-90, NRLMSISE-00, and NRLMSISE-2.0), Jacchia 70, and DTM models in their respective studies (Bruinsma, 2015; Emmert et al., 2020; Hedin, 1987, 1991; Jacchia, 1970; Picone et al., 2002). The updated Naval Research Laboratory (NRLMSISE-00) empirical atmospheric model suffers from inherent limitations in satellite information for determining the composition and structure of the MLT atmosphere, particularly below 100 km (Picone et al., 2002). The NRLMSIS2-0 empirical

model, an upgrade from the earlier version, NRLMSISE-00, has become the most recent. This model extends from the ground to the exosphere, characterizing the mean observed patterns of temperature and eight species densities. Whereas, artificial neural network-based models have recently drawn the attention of the research community across various disciplines due to their capacity to capture nonlinear relationships between inputs and outputs. Predictive models based on neural networks (NN) can often outperform traditional physical and statistical methods ([Tran et al., 2021](#)).

However, previous studies have considered a single parameter to analyze MLT dynamics and their variabilities at mid and high latitudes; studies at low latitudes are scarce, which is the impetus for the current work. Therefore, using the reliable method of wavelet analysis and MLR approaches, this dissertation primarily focuses on MLT dynamics variability and trends based on long-term TIMED/SABER temperature and ozone data over low latitude regions (3-15⁰N). Additionally, the spatial variability of MLT inversions and their associated inductive gravity wave is investigated. Due to the dearth of long-term and continuous data, there were no significant findings on equatorial MLT variability utilizing state-of-the-art Neural Network approaches. Finally, this research focuses on creating a NN-MLT model and predicting MLT temperature variability at low latitudes.

1.2 Statement of Problem

The MLT region is coupled to the lower and the upper atmosphere through the dynamics of MLT variability, thermal structure, and general circulations. MLT region is very important to balance or protect the stability of the lower atmosphere for comfortable human life on Earth by absorbing the high ultraviolet radiation from the solar system. Over the last decade, our knowledge of the MLT has been expanded through observations and models with studies mainly focused on describing and understanding its dynamics and variability.

The long-term variability of MLT temperature and ozone needs to be investigated to better characterize MLT dynamics, taking into account the effects of intra-annual (SAO and AO) and inter-annual (ENSO, QBO, and SC) variability. In addition to the influence of natural oscillations the role of atmospheric waves, particularly gravity waves, as a causative component in the MLT inversion phenomenon needs to be further investigated in order to better understand the MLT dynamics. Although inversion phenomena have been the focus of numerous studies in

MLT dynamics, whereas formation mechanisms across low-latitudes remain poorly understood due to a lack of long-term observations. The effect of gravity waves in MIL inversions based on temperature variability needs to be explored using potential energy to estimate the extent and impact on the upper and lower MIL inversions. The Brunt-Vaisala frequency is also required to explore the MLT instability.

Additional research was required to develop a model that could be compared to the observation and other physical models already in existence using continuous and reliable data. An awareness of the temperature in the MLT region was important in developing an independent atmospheric NN-MLT model. Such models are potentially important tools for understanding the dynamics of the joint MLT regions by filling gaps in ground-based and satellite-based observations. Three important issues regarding the dynamics of the MLT variability were addressed in order to achieve this.

- (1) What drivers (factors) are important for low latitude MLT variability?
- (2) Do multiple inversions occur in the low-latitude MLT dynamic region? If so, what are their underlying causes?
- (3) When creating a NN-MLT model, can the neural network (NN) technique capture the diversity in MLT dynamics?

The following objectives were designed to solve the aforementioned problems.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The research described in this dissertation focuses on the variability of highly dynamic MLT regions of the Earth's atmosphere in order to better understand the dynamics influenced by various drivers. The following are the specific goals of this investigation:

- I.** Long-term temperature and ozone variability and its response to natural drivers in the MLT region using 16 years (2005-2020) of TIMED/SABER observation data over low-latitude (3-15⁰N).
- II.** The Role of Gravity Waves in the Mesosphere-Lower-Thermosphere (MLT) Inversions over low-latitude (3-15⁰N)
- III.** NN-MLT Model Prediction for Low-Latitude MLT Regions Based on Neural-Network and Long-term SABER Observation.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) region is a gateway between Earth's environment and space, where the Sun's energy is first deposited into Earth's environment. MLT region is very important to protect or balance the stability of the lower atmosphere for comfortable human life on Earth by absorbing the high ultraviolet radiation from the solar system, which is also important for the areas of space travel, radio wave propagation, space weather, and Aurora. Observational and modeling studies of the MLT dynamics of physical variables (e.g. temperature, and ozone) under natural influences are of great use for monitoring the rate of climactic change. The measurement of the atmospheric temperature variability is important to answer fundamental questions about the nature of the ozone layer depletion crisis and its impact on the thermal structures. Whereas the study of inversion phenomena is important for our comprehensive understanding of middle and upper (MLT) atmospheric dynamics. In the inversion stops the decrement of temperature with elevation and instead becomes warmer. The inversion layer, which acts like a cap on the upward movement of air from the layers below, with pollutants (like fog, smog, dust particles, and smoke) has a significant factor in the formation of cloud. As a result, the temperature inversion phenomenon prevents these air pollutants traveling to the upper thermosphere region. Instead, they invert the natural state of hot and cold air, trapping the air contaminants from the earth surface. Whereas, the long-term observations is very important in order to comprehensively develop our model NN-MLT for the MLT atmospheric dynamics investigation and to forecast MLT weather conditions temperature. Space tourism has recently grown popular among the ultra-rich, forcing the need for measurements and models to reach higher into the atmosphere in order to provide so-called space weather forecast. As a result, modelers must have thorough understanding of the MLT region.

1.5 Dissertation Outline

This doctoral dissertation focuses on the characteristics of atmospheric waves, particularly gravity waves and natural oscillations impact in the MLT region, and modeling based on the data acquired from satellite-based observation data, with the assistance of empirical data from the NRLMSISE2.0 model and some proxy data, quasi-Biennial east-west zonal winds, Nino3.4, and F10.7 solar radio flux for QBO, ENSO, and SCO oscillations respectively. The dissertation was

conducted from two perspectives: One studied the impacts of natural oscillations and the dissipation of energy from gravity waves in their propagation on the dynamics of mesospheric and lower thermosphere (MLT) regions. The other one is modeling based on neural network techniques using the long-time period SABER observation data to fill the gap between satellite and ground-based observations for the MLT region over low latitudes for the first time.

The whole dissertation is organized into Seven Chapters, described as follows: Chapter 1 contains a general introduction to the study. A brief description of the motivation for the objectives, with justifications, and the significance of the study were presented. Chapter 2: Within this chapter, an attempt is made to give general descriptions of the Earth's atmospheric system and its dynamics of thermal structure and variability under the influence of atmospheric wave processes and atmospheric oscillations. In Chapter 3, the instrumentation and data analysis techniques used in the study are presented. Chapters 4–6 consists, the details of each objective implemented in the investigations as follows: The Long-term temperature and ozone response to natural drivers in the MLT region using 16 years (2005–2020) of TIMED/SABER observation data over low latitude is presented in Chapter 4. Chapter 5 presents an Investigation of the role of Gravity Waves in the MLT Inversions over low latitudes. Whereas Chapter 6 presented the NN-MLT Model Prediction for Low-Latitude regions based on artificial neural networks and Long-Term SABER Observations. Finally, the dissertation's Chapter 7 presented the conclusions and suggestions for potential directions for further research.

CHAPTER TWO

2. The Earth-atmosphere System

The Earth's atmosphere is the gaseous matter retained by Earth's gravity that surrounds the planet and is one of the fundamental components of Earth's interconnected physical systems. The atmosphere is very important for the existence of life on Earth as it absorbs the high energy ultraviolet and x-ray solar radiation from the source to the Earth's surface and protects us from harmful ultraviolet solar radiation from the sun. The study of Earth's atmosphere is essential to understanding the planet's climate, weather patterns, and solar activities. These atmospheric phenomena resulted in continuous solar radiation exchange between the atmosphere, the Earth's surface, and space. On average, 51% of the solar radiation is absorbed by the Earth's surface, with the remaining 19% absorbed by the atmosphere and 30% reflected by the atmosphere's system. The Earth's surface and the atmosphere maintain an equilibrium state of energy by reemitting the absorbed energy to space as thermal-infrared or long-wave radiation. The absorbed and re-emitted energy is responsible for the dynamics of the atmosphere, ranging from micro to planetary scales. Hence, the composition, thermal structure, and dynamics with their phenomenon and processes of the Earth's atmosphere need to be thoroughly understood.

2.1 Atmospheric Composition

The earth's atmosphere is composed of a group of gases with permanent and variable constituents. The primary permanent gases are Nitrogen, oxygen, and argon, along with other trace gases as mentioned in Table 2.1, which account for more than 99.96% of the atmosphere by volume up to an altitude of about 100 km, and the rest are inconsistent constituents. The extent of the primary permanent composition of the atmosphere is approximately 78% nitrogen (N_2), 21% oxygen (O_2), and 0.93% argon (Ar), including the remaining minor and very influential constituent trace gases, less than 0.1%, such as neon (Ne), helium (He), methane (CH_4), krypton (Kr), hydrogen (H_2), and carbon dioxide (CO_2). The percentage of the volume of the atmosphere occupied by most of these gases is nearly constant as one moves horizontally through the lower portion of the atmosphere as shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Composition of Earth's atmospheric gases (either atoms or molecules) based on volume in percentage.

Ozone and water, along with other variables listed in Table 2.1, are inconsistent since both of them do not have constant atmospheric volumes. For instance, Ozone is concentrated mainly in the range between 15 and 35 km, and its volume mixing ratio is low over the equator relative to the poleward latitudes. One important exception to this is water vapor, which can vary dramatically in both horizontal and vertical directions. Unlike the other gases that make up the atmosphere, water vapor makes up a highly variable percentage by volume of the atmosphere because of the range of conditions within it. Indeed, the amount of water vapor can range from close to zero to 4% of the total volume. Additionally, water vapor can undergo phase changes to both the liquid and solid state, and water can exist simultaneously as a gas, liquid, and solid in a given volume of the atmosphere. Changes in the phase of water in the atmosphere release or absorb large quantities of heat which can be important in driving the dynamics of the atmosphere. The water vapor primarily enters the mesosphere from two sources: the first is advection and mixing of water vapor from lower altitudes, and the second is the photo-dissociation of methane (Thomas and Olivero, 2001). While the atmosphere is a mixture of all those various gases, its state can nevertheless be approximated using the ideal gas law.

Table 2. 1The Composition of the Atmosphere

<u>Permanent constitute variable constitutes</u>			
Constituent	% by volume	Constituent	% by volume
Nitrogen (N ₂)	78.084	water vapor (H ₂ O)	0-0.04
Oxygen (O ₂)	20.948	Ozone (O ₃)	0-12 x 10 ⁻⁴
Argon (Ar)	0.934	Sulfur dioxide (SO ₂)	0.001 x 10 ⁻⁴
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	0.036	Nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂)	0.001 x 10 ⁻⁴
Neon (Ne)	18.18 x 10 ⁻⁴	Ammonia (NH ₃)	0.004 x 10 ⁻⁴
Helium (He)	5.24 x 10 ⁻⁴	Nitric oxide (NO)	0.0005 x 10 ⁻⁴
Krypton (Kr)	1.14 x 10 ⁻⁴	Hydrogen sulfide (H ₂ S)	0.00005 x 10 ⁻⁴
Xenon (Xe)	0.089 x 10 ⁻⁴	Nitric acid vapor (HNO ₃)	Trace
Hydrogen (H ₂)	0.5 x 10 ⁻⁴	Chlorofluorocarbons	Trace
Methane (CH ₄)	1.7 x 10 ⁻⁴	(CFCl ₃ , CF ₂ Cl ₂	
Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	0.3 x 10 ⁻⁴	CH ₃ , CCl ₃ , CCl ₄ , etc.)	
Carbon monoxide (CO)	0.08 x 10 ⁻⁴		

In addition to these gases, the atmosphere has a wide variety of tiny particles suspended in the air. These various kinds of atmospheric variabilities-aerosols, clouds, and precipitation- affect atmospheric dynamics, which are highly variable in space and time. The effect of atmospheric aerosols perturbs the total amount of short-wave radiation by absorbing or scattering incoming radiation, thereby influencing atmospheric dynamics. The aerosol particles such as dust, smoke, organic matter, sea salt, etc. are known to be produced by natural processes, including volcanic dust and human activity from forest fires. Whereas another atmospheric variabilities cloud can form in the cold summer mesosphere in the presence of dust and water vapor. The dust is generally thought to be of volcanic origin or come from meteors in the upper atmosphere. Based on the composition of these gases and particles, the atmospheric dynamics are diverse.

2.2 Thermal Structure

Fundamental parameters such as temperature, pressure, and components of the wind in dynamic studies are those that give the physical state of the atmosphere. Therefore, the Earth's atmosphere can be divided into different layers according to its characteristics based on the vertical gradient of the parameter temperature at different altitudes. The temperature in a neutral atmosphere generally serves to divide into four regions according to the International Union of

Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG) standard nomenclature set in 1960: the troposphere (extending from the Earth’s surface to altitudes of about 10–16 km), the stratosphere (10–16 km to 50 km), the mesosphere (50–80 km), the thermosphere (80–500 km), and further, the ionosphere region (60–1000 km). The boundaries separating these atmospheric regions are called pauses such as tropopause, stratopause, mesopause, and else. The atmosphere, including the troposphere, stratosphere, and mesosphere, where neutral species are well mixed by turbulence and other processes, is often referred to as the homosphere. Above the homosphere in the thermosphere, diffusive separation gradually overtakes, and the concentrations of the different species drop off differently with increasing altitude, depending on their weights. In the upper atmosphere, neutral mass density can demonstrate significant geographical and temporal variations. Figure 2.2 shows the classification of different regions of the Earth’s atmosphere on the basis of temperature.

Figure 2.2: Vertical temperature profile of the Earth’s atmosphere describing different regions and the solar radiations being absorbed at different altitudes. Source: <http://www.theozonhole.com/atmosphere.htm>

The troposphere is the lowest part of the atmosphere and extends up to 8 km at the poles, whereas in the tropics it extends up to 16 km. This part of the atmosphere is the densest layer; the temperature drops from about 300 to 210 K. The temperature generally decreases with the height in the troposphere. The rate of temperature decrease is about 6.5 K/km (called the lapse rate), which is called the environmental lapse rate. For dry air, the lapse rate is called dry adiabatic

lapse rate, $\Gamma = g/c_p$, its value is approximately 9.8 K/km. The atmosphere within this part naturally becomes unstable due to the negative lapse rate (i.e., $\gamma = \frac{1}{T} \frac{dT}{dy}$) (Rishbet; Gariott, 1969).

Whereas the temperature increments with altitude in the troposphere, the inversion exists. The tropical troposphere is basically an unstable region and convective processes transport heat, water vapor, and trace constituents to higher altitudes. Thus, the exchange of layers between the troposphere and stratosphere in the cross-sectional region is tropopause, which is a turning point in the temperature profile from a negative to a positive lapse rate. The vertical transport of air and chemical species through the depths of the tropical troposphere can occur on time scales as short as a few hours via moist convection (Holton et al., 1995).

The stratosphere is the second lower layer of the Earth's atmosphere above the tropopause and it extends up to 50 km high. Compared to the troposphere, this part of the atmosphere is dry and less dense. In this region, the temperature rises with increasing altitude. Due to the ozone layer's ability to absorb ultraviolet (UV) radiation, the temperature gradually rises to 270 K. This high concentration of ozone then re-emits this energy in the form of heat into the stratosphere to warm the region as well as prevent an intense flux of ultraviolet radiation from reaching the surface. This positive lapse rate and stably stratified region contain various types of waves, for example, atmospheric gravity waves and tides carry energy from the troposphere upward into the stratosphere and transport energy from this region up to the mesosphere. The waves and tides influence the flow of air and can cause regional heating in the stratosphere. The region is bounded at the top by the stratopause where the temperature stops increasing and reverts back to a negative lapse rate (Mohanakumar, 2008). The stratosphere region, including the troposphere, contains 99% of the atmosphere. The stratosphere is separated from the next layer of the mesosphere by the layer of stratopause.

The mesosphere is a layer that extends from 50 to ~ 100 km and is characterized by a decrease in temperature with increasing altitude. The region is considered to be the coldest of Earth's atmosphere reaching a minimum of 180 K at 80 km altitude. In contrast to the stratosphere, the mesosphere has a negative temperature lapse rate and is primarily cooled by radiative emissions from carbon dioxide (CO₂). Modeling studies suggest that a doubling of CO₂ and CH₄ in the atmosphere would yield a net cooling in the mesosphere between 10 and 50 K (Roble and Dickinson, 1989). In a manner of thinking, the mesosphere is a resumption of the troposphere after the rude interruption of the ozone layer in the stratosphere. It is much quieter up there since

the mesosphere is not in contact with the forces disturbing the air in the troposphere. The peculiar thermal effect of this region is that the summer mesopause is much cooler than its winter counterpart, though it is continuously bathed in sunlight. This is due to the existence of a high-altitude summer-to-winter meridional circulation, which flows from the summer to the winter polar region. The atmospheric wave processes gravity wave, planetary wave, and tidal waves carry their energy and momentum transferred from the troposphere and deposited into the mesosphere. The dynamical processes of waves and their upward transport of momentum influence the mesospheric temperature. A temperature inversion layer is formed in the mesosphere where the temperature lapse rate reverses its sign from positive to negative. For these mesospheric inversion layers ([Whiteway; Carswell, 1995](#)) atmospheric waves and chemical heating are responsible. The region of the inversion layer of enhanced temperature can be caused through the breaking of gravity waves associated with the regions of convective or shear instabilities ([Meriwether; Gardner, 2000](#)). In which the atmospheric gravity waves play the most important role in the dynamic processes of the atmosphere. The remaining atmosphere above the mesosphere is known as the thermosphere. As its name suggests, the temperatures here are large and increase monotonically with height due to the increasing photoionization of various chemical species.

The thermosphere includes the ionosphere extends out to several hundred kilometers. The thermosphere is a region of high temperature and very low density. The increment in temperature is due to the absorption of intense solar radiation by atomic oxygen and nitrogen, which is the major heating mechanism in the thermosphere. The intense Extreme ultraviolet (EUV) and X-ray photons break electrons away from gas particles in the thermosphere, producing electrically charged ions of atoms and molecules (mainly N_2^+ , O_2^+ and O^+ in the lower thermosphere), which is called the ionosphere. The ionosphere is of practical importance because it makes possible long-distance radio communications. The neutral thermosphere overlaps in altitude with the ionosphere which extends from ~ 85 km to ~ 1000 km ([Kelley, 1989; Schunk and Nagy, 2000](#)). Winds and overall circulation in the thermosphere are driven largely by the atmospheric tides and gravity waves. Beyond the thermosphere, the region is called the exosphere, where interplanetary space starts.

2.3 The Mesosphere and Lower Thermosphere (MLT) Dynamics

The Earth's atmosphere, especially the Mesosphere Lower Thermosphere (MLT) region, is affected by complex interactions. The MLT region extends from the upper mesosphere (~60 km) to the lower thermosphere ~110 km ([Andrews et al., 1987](#); [Vincent, 2015](#)) with a negative and positive temperature gradient. The unstable mesosphere and lower thermosphere regions are home to some of the most spectacular optical and dynamic phenomena in Earth's atmosphere. Since the region is exposed to the lower influence of the atmospheric waves (planetary, tidal, and gravity waves) from the troposphere and to the upper influence of x-ray and ultraviolet solar radiation. The upper mesosphere and lower thermosphere contain some part of the ionosphere region with their charged atoms and molecules (ions). The constituents at this level include nitrogen gas (N), atomic oxygen (O), and nitric oxide (NO). All these are exposed to solar emission of ultraviolet and x-ray radiation, which can result in ionization, by knocking off an atom or molecule to form an electron with a positive charge. This charged particle in the MLT region is known as the ionosphere. The ionosphere is not a distinct atmospheric layer, but rather a series of regions located in parts of the mesosphere and thermosphere (MLT).

The MLT is the least studied portion of Earth's atmosphere primarily due to extreme difficulty in making measurements in this region has led many scientists to jokingly refer to the MLT as the "ignosphere". The region is located above and below in the most range of measurements. It is too high for aircraft or balloon measurements and too low for satellite orbits for in situ measurements. Thus, owing to this lack of measurements the region remained one of the least explored regions of the Earth's atmosphere. For continuous observations the remote sensing techniques have been used to study the MLT region. These remote sensing observations over the past decade improved our understanding of the MLT region therefore this region is now no more an "ignorosphere".

The mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) regions of the atmosphere. MLT dynamics play a very important role in quantifying the influences from above (i.e., solar radiation) and from below (i.e., atmospheric waves), which affect the MLT region in various ways. Recently, MLT dynamics have been reviewed by several authors that describe some key phenomena in the MLT region ([Shepherd, 2000](#)), processes that control the circulation in the MLT region ([Becker, 2012](#)), and processes involved with the interaction between the lower, middle, and upper atmospheres ([Smith, 2012b](#)). Processes that derive the MLT atmospheric dynamics are

differential heating of the atmosphere, radiative transfer, and photochemistry, as well as waves and oscillations. The atmospheric waves (Gravity waves, tides, and planetary waves) that are generated in the lower atmosphere propagate up and influence the dynamics of the MLT region, thereby changing the thermal structure and variability. Therefore, it is apparent that the contribution of wave effect is accounted for obtaining the observed circulation and thermal structure in the MLT atmospheric region. Hence, it is vitally important to understand the role of wave dynamics in the middle atmosphere in order to enhance our understanding of the processes involved in various regions of the atmosphere. Further, the dynamics of the thermal structure and variabilities of the MLT region were investigated in various processes. In the following sections, some of these processes and their effect on the MLT dynamic region will be described.

2.4 Atmospheric Oscillations/waves influence on MLT dynamics

Waves are periodic motions of Earth's atmosphere that have various spatial (from meters to thousands of kilometers) and temporal scales (from minutes to months) as a disturbance that propagates in space and time. The mesosphere and lower thermosphere dynamics composition, structure, circulation, and variability are understood based on the most relevant atmospheric waves (tidal wave, planetary wave, and gravity wave) or oscillations (Semi-annual, annual, Quasi-biennial, solar cycle, and El Niño–Southern oscillation). Atmospheric waves were being observed and their theory developed, and their influences were largely ignored (Fritts, 1984; Hines, 1989). Despite this, observational and theoretical development in the field of the atmospheric field continues. Then in the late 1960s, atmospheric waves were demonstrated to derive the dynamics of the equatorial middle atmosphere by Lindzen and Holton (1968). Since then, the atmosphere has been identified, and waves have greatly aided in understanding the dynamics of those atmospheric regions.

2.4.1 Observations of Periodic Oscillations in MLT Region

The tropical variability can be addressed through the leading driving mechanisms of the MLT to understand their dynamics over the low latitude region based on the long-term oscillations such as semiannual, annual, Quasi-biennial, solar cycle of F10.7, and El Niño–Southern Oscillations (SAO, AO, QBO, ENSO, and SC) in Figure 2.3. These oscillations have been observed in winds, ozone volume mixing ratio (OVMR), temperature, and other atmospheric fields to investigate the dynamics in the middle atmospheric thermal structure, circulation, and variability. A brief

description of these long-term oscillations in the middle atmosphere is given in the following: Seasonal oscillations (SAO and AO) are well-known atmospheric influences in equatorial regions and are major sources of intra-annual variations (Yue et al., 2019; Ern et al., 2015). Semiannual oscillation (SAO) has periods of around 6 months and was first observed (Reed, 1966) in the middle atmosphere using zonal wind data. Subsequently to this work using temperature data, it was shown that SAO is present throughout the mesosphere (Groves, 1972; Hirota, 1978; Garcia et al., 1997). In the tropical middle atmosphere, including the MLT region, the semiannual oscillation (SAO) in the mean zonal temperature is an important feature. The MLT SAO is out of phase over the equatorial latitude (Garcia et al., 1997). The forcing of the SAO is not so well understood, but it is believed to be entirely wave-driven. The Annual Oscillation (AO) is also observed in the middle atmosphere, which has a period of around 12 months. The annual oscillation in the mean zonal wind is fundamentally driven by the annual cycle in solar insolation (Andrews et al., 1987). Similarly, the study of Nath and Sridharan (2014) found the impacts of the oscillations SAO and AO on the mesospheric temperature variability to understand their dynamics based on the SABER measurements.

In addition to the seasonal oscillations (SAO and AO), including natural influences like Quasi-Biennial Oscillation (QBO), El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO), and solar cycle (SC), has become crucial to accurately understand the MLT dynamics based on their variability (Kishore et al., 2014; Li et al., 2013). Even our investigation results support them. The quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO) is a tropical phenomenon of downward propagating westward and eastward winds in the equatorial stratosphere with a variable period from 22 to 34 months and an average period of 28 months (Baldwin et al., 2001). It also influenced the circulation in the polar middle atmosphere (Holton and Tan, 1980).

El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is an ocean-atmosphere coupled phenomenon. The El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) manifests as inter-annual variability in sea surface temperature, wind, and pressure in the eastern tropical Pacific as a warm phase (El Niño) when the index exceeds 0.5°C and a cold phase (La Niña) when the index is less than -0.5°C for at least five consecutive over-lapping seasons. The commonly used index to represent the ENSO oscillation is the 3-month running mean of sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies using the Niño 3.4 index in the region of (5°N to 5°S) latitude and (170°W to 120°W) longitude of the tropical Pacific ocean based on centered 30-year base periods updated every five years. ENSO is

the one that influences lower and middle atmospheric variability to understand their dynamics. ENSO has global climate effects through oceanic and atmospheric teleconnections (Liu and Alexander, 2007). The influences of ENSO on atmospheric temperature variation are significant, not only at the tropics around the equator within the troposphere, but also at middle and high latitudes as well as in the stratosphere (Seager et al., 2003; Free and Seidel, 2009; Randel et al., 2009; Scherllin-Pirscher et al., 2012). QBO and ENSO influences on the middle atmospheric temperature were studied by Li et al. (2008, 2013) and Domeisen et al. (2019) and ozone by Olsen et al. (2019).

Figure 2.3: Vertical distribution of the amplitude of the MQBO, MSAO, SSAO, SQBO, and annual component at the equator (Adapted from Baldwin et al., 2001).

The atmosphere is not only affected internally through dynamics but also by external forcing from above, which is the solar activity known as solar radio flux (F10.7). The variability in the incoming solar shortwave radiation is known to drive the atmosphere on decadal, annual and seasonal scales. In our investigations, it has been determined that the MLT region's temperature responds to solar activity. There are some indices that are used to calculate the sun's solar

activity level. One often used indicator of solar activity (solar cycle oscillation) is the F10.7 solar radio flux. The sun's cyclical changes have an effect on the MLT region. The MLT region is particularly vulnerable to extreme ultraviolet (EUV) sun radiation. In this dissertation, solar 10.7 cm radio flux (F10.7) is utilized as a proxy data, and its effect on MLT temperature and ozone is clearly obvious, as detailed in the following chapters.

2.4.2 Wave activity in MLT Region

In addition to the influence of seasonal (SAO and AO) and natural (QBO, ENSO, and SCO) oscillations, the dynamics of the MLT region are also dominated by atmospheric waves: the planetary wave, tide wave, and the gravity waves and their pictorial representation is shown in Figure (2.4). These atmospheric demonstration waves can propagate in horizontally and vertically in upward directions without interacting with the background atmosphere unless they are dissipating. Their horizontal scales vary dramatically from less than 10 km to several thousand kilometers, with vertical scales ranging from less than 10 to 40-50 km (Cai et al., 2017). Their oscillation periods can vary between a few minutes to approximately the Earth's intrinsic period (Li et al., 2007; Cai et al., 2014; Yuan et al., 2016; Cai et al., 2017). Such atmospheric waves are most important to characterize the dynamical behavior of the mesosphere and lower thermosphere. Three features of these waves are important: generation, propagation, and dissipation. The generation will receive less attention because the bulk of the wave activity in the MLT originates below, in the troposphere or stratosphere. Even, secondary waves that are created by the interactions of waves can be generated anywhere in the system (e.g., Gossard and Hooke, 1975; Gill, 1982; Andrews et al., 1987). While propagating, these waves interact with the background and dissipate their energy and momentum, which contribute to the atmospheric field of temperature variability in the region. Thus, these waves create a greatly coupled system and act as a carrier for transporting energy, and momentum from one part of the atmosphere to another (Andrews et al., 1987; Forbes, 1995).

Figure 2.4: The Schematic diagram of the atmospheric dynamic processes in the Earth's.

Atmospheric tides are global-scale oscillations in the atmosphere. The large-scale dynamics in the MLT are dominated by the solar atmospheric tides. The solar atmospheric tides are excited by periodic absorption of solar radiation of different spectral ranges at different altitudes e.g., near-infrared by tropospheric water vapor, ultraviolet by stratospheric ozone, and extreme ultraviolet by the major constituents like O_2 and N_2 in the lower thermosphere (Forbes and Groves, 1987; Forbes, 1995). They are also excited by nonlinear interactions between global-scale waves (Hagan et al., 2001; McLandress et al., 2000), and interactions between tides and gravity waves (McCandless and Ward, 1994). At any given height, the day-night variation in the absorbed radiation due to differential heating gives rise to periods that are integral to a solar day: 24 hours, 12 hours, and 8 hours and are referred to as the diurnal tide, semidiurnal tide, and Teri diurnal tide respectively. In the lower MLT region, the tide is mainly semidiurnal whereas in the upper MLT and thermosphere it is diurnal (Hargreaves, 1992).

Planetary waves (PWs) are large-scale oscillations in the atmosphere. Planetary waves (PWs) have typical periods of 2 days to 16 days (Dunkerton, 1991; Salby, 1981a, b). The horizontal propagation of PWs can either travel eastward/westward or remain stationary with respect to the background zonal flow. Our concern is less since stationary PWs are driven modes that are generated and maintained in the troposphere by topographic features like mountain ranges and the contrasts in land/ocean heating, which have no more effects on the MLT region. PWs are

often called Rossby waves and are generated due to the latitudinal gradient of the Coriolis force that balances variations of the pressure gradient force. However, these waves are present mainly at middle- and high latitudes, although sometimes they can move to lower latitudes. Further, kelvin waves (KW) are eastward-propagating planetary waves and are generated due to the Coriolis force at low latitudes, away from the equator. KWs play an important role in the lower stratosphere's dynamics, e.g., in forcing the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO), and have very large vertical wavelengths. These waves are capable of propagating upwards and reaching the middle atmospheric region ([Hirota, 1978](#); [Hirota, 1979](#); [Forbes et al., 2009](#)), coupling the MLT region with the lower atmosphere. However, at higher altitudes, the role of gravity waves becomes more important.

Theory of Gravity Waves

A gravity wave is a type of atmospheric wave that has gravity as its restoring force. Most gravity waves are generated in the troposphere/stratosphere through severe atmospheric disturbances, such as thunderstorms or jet streams to reach the MLT region or even the upper thermosphere. These propagated gravity waves can be distributed from their source regions across the atmosphere and become saturated at the critical level, thereby breaking and dissipating the vertical propagating waves, transferring their energy and momentum into the atmospheric background field, and thus considerably affecting its structure and variability of the atmosphere ([Andrews et al., 1987](#); [Holton et al., 2003](#); [Holton and Hakim, 2013](#)). The role of gravity wave propagation and dissipation has been accepted as the dominant wave forcing in the MLT region ([Lindzen, 1981](#); [Holton, 1983](#)). This dynamical influence of gravity wave motion arises from the restoring forces of gravity acting downward and buoyancy acting upward on vertically displaced air parcels. The influence of gravity waves on atmospheric dynamics is expressed mathematically based on theoretical concepts of air parcels that govern GWs as follows.

An external Gravity and buoyancy force will have a greater impact on the air parcel, which is an identifiable mass of air in static equilibrium, to displace it from its equilibrium position in the direction of the disturbance. The presence of one or more restoring forces in the atmosphere counteracts these disturbances, and a balance between these two forces results in wave motions. When an air parcel is placed at a greater altitude, the buoyancy force surrounding it reduces because of the exponentially decreasing air density and pressure, which causes the air parcel to slow down until it eventually turns around and begins to descend again. During the course of its

downward movement, the buoyancy force steadily increases again, and the parcel will overshoot its initial position due to inertia and sink to regions where the buoyancy force exceeds gravity. At some point, the positive buoyancy becomes sufficiently strong to reverse the air parcel's downward movement, causing it to move upward again. Thus, a vertical oscillation of the air parcel is generated. We call this type of oscillation an atmospheric gravity wave because gravity is part of the restoring force. These waves are manifested in the spatial and temporal changes of field variables such as pressure, temperature, and wind.

Thus, to express the motion of air parcels oscillation in terms of an equation, we assume that an identifiable mass of air parcel in its initial rest position has the same density, pressure, and temperature as those of the background. Another assumption is that the vertical motion of the air parcel is adiabatic (no heat exchange with the background) and hydrostatic (pressure within the air parcel and the background are the same). If the air parcel's and background pressure (p), as well as density (ρ), are equal in a static atmosphere, the hydrostatic equation becomes based on the governing equation and is thus expressed as [Liu \(2011\)](#):

Recall that the pressure distribution in the vertical for the atmosphere at rest can be represented in part by the hydrostatic pressure, denoted p_0 :

$$\rho = \rho_0, \quad p = p_0, \quad \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial p_0}{\partial z} = -g\rho_0 \quad (2.1)$$

$\gamma = c_p/c_v$, the ratio of the heat capacity at constant pressure and volume of adiabatic index

$$d \ln \rho = \frac{d \ln p}{\gamma} \quad (2.2)$$

The air parcel is denoted with a subscription (₀) symbol, while the background atmosphere doesn't have a subscription. Whereas other quantities to express the air parcel as z , g , γ , c_p , and c_v are altitude, gravity, adiabatic index, and heat capacity at certain pressures and volumes, respectively used in the adiabatic equation (2.2) as well as hydrostatic equation (2.1). Since the motion of the air parcel is assumed to be adiabatic; its density will differ from that of the background once it starts to move away from its initial equilibrium altitude.

Here another important concept of potential temperature is introduced, which stands for the air parcel's temperature when it is displaced adiabatically to a standard pressure level, p_0 , from the current pressure level, p . The potential temperature (θ) is based on the first law of thermodynamics:

$$\frac{dT}{T} = \frac{R}{c_p} \frac{dp}{p} \Rightarrow \int_T^0 \frac{dT}{T} = \int_p^{p_0} \frac{R}{c_p} \frac{dp}{p} \quad (2.3) \text{ it yields}$$

$$\theta = T \left(\frac{p_0}{p} \right)^{R/c_p} \quad (2.4)$$

R is the gas constant per unit mass, P₀ the reference pressure and T the current temperature of the air parcel. Whereas the motion of the vertical atmospheric air parcel can be described in equation (2.5) due to the Buoyant and gravitational forces acts on the parcel as shown in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: A schematic representation of the air parcel model. The blue square is the air parcel. The black double arrow represents the displacement, ds . The angle relative to the horizontal direction is α . The air parcel is influenced by two forces: gravity (mg) and buoyancy force (F_b). **Notice** that the direction of the displacement, ds , is not vertical but at an angle α relative to the horizontal plane. Therefore, the equation of motion can be described as follows by Liu (2011) to calculate the Brunt-Vaisala frequency of the parcel:

$$\frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = -g \frac{\rho - \rho_0}{\rho} \sin \alpha \quad (2.5)$$

Based on the hydrostatic equation (2.1) and the ideal gas law, $\rho = p/RT = p_0/RT$ the parcels equation (2.6) becomes

$$\frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = \frac{g}{\rho} \left(\frac{d\rho}{dp} \frac{\partial p_0}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial \rho_0}{\partial z} \right) z \quad (2.6)$$

Following the same approach using the hydrostatic equation (2.1) and the adiabatic equation (2.2) substitute into equation (2.6) becomes

$$\frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = \frac{g}{\rho} \left(\frac{\rho}{\gamma p_0} \frac{\partial p_0}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial \rho_0}{\partial z} \right) z = g \left(\frac{\partial \ln \rho_0}{\partial z} - \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{\partial \ln p_0}{\partial z} \right) z \quad (2.7)$$

For the ideal gas law of $p = \rho RT$, taken the natural logarithm on both sides and the partial derivative with respect to altitude, z , yielding $\frac{\partial \ln \rho}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial \ln p}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial \ln T}{\partial z}$.

In a similar approach, the potential temperature (θ) of atmospheric parcels from equation (2.4) becomes

$$\frac{\partial \ln \theta}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial \ln T}{\partial z} - \frac{R}{c_p} \frac{\partial \ln p}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \frac{g}{c_p} \right) \quad (2.8)$$

Based on equation (2.6) and (2.7), equation (2.8) becomes

$$\frac{\partial \ln \theta}{\partial z} = \left(1 - \frac{R}{c_p} \right) \frac{\partial \ln p}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial \ln p}{\partial z} \quad (2.9)$$

Again the parcel motion of an acceleration from equations (2.7) becomes to in the following

$$\frac{d^2 s}{dt^2} = -g \frac{\partial \ln \theta_0}{\partial z} z \sin a = -g \frac{\partial \ln \theta_0}{\partial z} ds \cdot \sin^2 a \quad (2.10)$$

Whereas by introducing the Brunt-Vaisala frequency, N , with $N^2 = g \frac{\partial \ln \theta_0}{\partial z}$

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \frac{g}{c_p} \right) = \frac{g}{T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \Gamma_a \right) \quad (2.11)$$

Finally, it is possible to rewrite the equation that describes the motion of the air parcel in the atmosphere as:

$$\frac{d^2 s}{dt^2} = -(N \sin a)^2 s \quad (2.12)$$

The Brunt-Vaisala frequency (N) in equation (2.8) is the basis on which we can formulate the potential energy of the gravity waves.

$$E_p(z) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{g(z)}{N(z)} \right)^2 \left(\frac{T_p(z)}{T_0(z)} \right)^2 \quad (2.13)$$

The potential energy used to know by what extent the atmospheric gravity wave influences the atmospheric dynamics.

2.5 MLT Inversion Layers (MILs)

The mesospheric inversion layers (MILs), also known as mesospheric temperature inversions (MTIs), are the narrow thermal layers of the vertical temperature gradient from negative to positive that are formed in the middle atmosphere, and even in MLT region. Their appearance was very similar to that of inversion layers in tropospheric temperature profiles near the ground (Meriwether and Gerrard, 2004). Since first observed by Schmidlin (1976), Mesospheric Inversion Layers (MIL) have been routinely observed in the MLT region using temperature measurements. Schmidlin recognized MILs as a regular climatological feature in the

mesospheric temperature profile. MILs are defined as a layer of increasing temperature in the mesosphere and represent a departure from the expected positive atmospheric lapse rate ($\Gamma = -\frac{\partial T}{\partial z}$). These MILs are seen in the MLT region at the low and mid-latitudes, particularly over the low latitudes, at any time of the year. Temperature inversions have been omnipresent features in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere regions for decades, and they have been comprehensively studied in the past by using all sorts of available techniques (e.g., lidar, radar, rocket sonde, and satellite) over different geographic locations. A typical structure of a MIL profile that might be observed with a Rayleigh/Na lidar system is depicted in Figure 2.6. In this observation, the MIL phenomenon was originally identified as a single layer near 70 km (lower MIL) with a typical thickness of 10–15 km and temperature enhancement of 20–100 K. The availability of more complete measurements of the temperature structure in the MLT region has indicated that multiple layers are more commonly observed as shown in Figure 2.6 than a single inversion layer at around 70 km. Recent studies have also concentrated on the dynamics of MILs (Gan et al., 2012; Walterscheid and Hickey, 2009), and the formation mechanisms associated with MILs (Collins et al., 2011; Szewczyk et al., 2013).

Figure 2.6: Schematic of upper and lower mesospheric inversion layers shown in the temperature profile for the MLT regions. Solid/dotted lines show with and without MILs (Adapted from Meriwether and Gerrard, 2004).

Gan et al., (2012) presented the global characteristics of the MIL based on the Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry (SABER) instrument aboard the Thermosphere Ionosphere Mesosphere Energetics Dynamics (TIMED) satellite from 2002 to 2010. However, the formation mechanism for MTIs is quite complex and has been a subject of debate since their first detection. Many formation mechanisms have been proposed in the literature, such as gravity wave breaking, nonlinear interactions of gravity waves and tides, chemical heating, planetary wave breaking, and dissipation, underscoring the complexity of the phenomenon (Wu, 2000; Salby et al., 2002; Sassi et al., 2002; Oberheide et al., 2006; Liu and Hagan, 1998; States and Gardner, 2000; Hauchecorne et al., 1987; Meriwether and Mlynczak, 1995; Meriwether and Gardner, 2000; Meriwether and Gerrard, 2004; Ramesh et al., 2013; Sharma et al., 2016).

The review by Meriwether and Gerrard (2004) identifies two types of MILs as the “upper” (~85-100 km) and “lower” MIL (~65-80 km) in an attempt to better quantify the complex physical processes responsible for their formation, the upper MIL is found at higher altitudes between 85 and 100 km is generated by a gravity wave. However, as illustrated in other investigations, the lower MIL is found at lower altitudes between 65 and 80 km. In addition to these wave activities, chemistry also has an impact on the creation of upper MILs in the MLT region. A number of exothermic chemical processes in the higher MLT regions are held to play a significant role as a causative mechanism for an inversion. Similarly, in this investigation, some effort has been made based on the SABER/TIMED satellite to understand the causative gravity waves of an inversion over the low latitudes. Wave breaking is the principal mechanism by which their energy and momentum dissipate into the background atmosphere as a causative to the lower and upper inversions.

CHAPTER THREE

3. Observations and Data Analysis Methods

Observational and model data were used to explore the dynamics of the mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) at low latitude (3-15⁰N) region. As previously stated, three separate data sources were used in this dissertation work: the TIMED/SABER satellite, the NRLMSISE2.0 empirical model, and proxy data of natural influences (QBO, ENSO, and SC).

3.1 TIMED/SABER Observation

The Earth's satellites are all operated over the Earth in their orbital locations to provide information about the Earth. Low-Earth orbit (often known as LEO) satellites are among those Earth satellites and encompass Earth-centered orbits with an altitude of 2,000 km or less but could be as low as 160 km above Earth. They are considered the area in Earth's orbit near enough to Earth compared to other orbits but still very far above Earth's surface and are commonly used for observations, Telecommunications, imaging, military reconnaissance, spying, and resupply. The orbit period of LEO, mainly depending on the altitude, varies in the range of 90-120 min. As the altitude of LEO satellites is low, their velocity is very high (>25,000 km/h), and they make 12-16 orbits per day (in 24 h). Most of the LEO satellites are used for Earth or space observation; the best example used in our investigation is the TIMED (Thermosphere, Ionosphere, Mesosphere Energetics, and Dynamics) observation satellite. The MLT atmosphere is a critical part of our Earth system and TIMED's long-term data set has been an important part of deepening our understanding of MLT dynamics. The TIMED mission is studying the influences of the Sun and humans on the least explored and understood region of Earth's atmosphere Mesosphere and Lower Thermosphere/Ionosphere (MLTI). The science objective of the TIMED mission is to understand the MLTI region's basic pressure, temperature, and wind structure and the spatial and temporal variations that result from the transfer of energy into and out of this region. It is to provide a better understanding of the properties of energy and its redistribution in the Mesosphere and Lower-Thermosphere/Ionosphere (MLTI) region to develop climatology of key atmospheric parameters (Remsberg et al., 2003; Mertens et al., 2004). As shown in Figure 3.1, the TIMED satellite is focusing on a portion of the atmospheric region located approximately (60-180 km) above the surface. The satellite was launched into an orbit

with a height of 625 km and an inclination of about 74.1° from the equator on December 7, 2001, with its orbital period of approximately 97 min. It scans Earth's horizon up and down once every 58 seconds and makes 15 orbits, providing ~1400 profiles per day with vertical and horizontal resolutions of ~2 km and 300 km, respectively. The data that are primarily used for the present study are those from one of the four instruments, such as GUVI (Global Ultraviolet Imager), SABER (Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry), SEE (Solar Extreme-Ultraviolet Experiment), and TIDI (TIMED Doppler Interferometer) aboard the NASA satellite Thermosphere-Ionosphere-Mesosphere Energetics and Dynamics (TIMED), called the Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry (SABER). All data products generated by the TIMED mission are nonproprietary and reside in the public domain through the World Wide Web (WWW).

Figure 3.1: The TIMED (Thermosphere, Ionosphere, Mesosphere Energetics, and Dynamics) orbital satellite position and observation views.

The primary goal of the SABER experiment is to provide the data needed to advance our understanding of the fundamental processes governing the energetics, chemistry, dynamics, and transport in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) region. The SABER instrument on board the TIMED satellite has measured temperature and several trace species profiles cover an altitude range from ~20 km to ~110 km since January 2002 and the latitude coverage shifts from 53°N – 83°S to 53°S – 83°N due to the yaw cycle about every 60 days (northward-viewing yaw,

switching after 60 days to corresponding southward-viewing yaw), Over the course of one orbit, SABER observes between about 52° S and 83° N. SABER accomplishes this with global as well as regional measurements of the atmosphere using a 10-channel broadband limb-scanning infrared radiometer covering the spectral range $1.27\ \mu\text{m}$ to $17\ \mu\text{m}$ (Russell et al. 1999) and it described in the Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: The temperature is derived based on 10-channel broadband limb-scanning infrared radiation from composition emissions.

These measurements are used to provide vertical profiles of kinetic temperature, pressure, geopotential height, volume mixing ratios for the trace species O₃, CO₂, H₂O, [O], and [H], volume emission rates for $5.3\ \mu\text{m}$ NO, $2.1\ \mu\text{m}$ OH, $1.6\ \mu\text{m}$ OH, and $1.27\ \mu\text{m}$ O₂ ($^1\Delta$), cooling and heating rates for many CO₂, O₃, and O₂ bands, and chemical heating rates. The kinetic temperature profiles are retrieved using a Non-Local Thermodynamically Equilibrium (LTE) inversion method. Mertens et al. (2001) and Remsberg et al. (2003) have demonstrated the accuracy of SABER temperatures retrieved assuming LTE and Non-LTE methods and the latter is found to be more accurate (Mertens et al. 2004). The details of SABER instrumentation and data products can be freely accessible through the web: <http://saber.gatsinc.com/index.php>.

3.2 NRLMSIS2.0 Empirical Model

In addition to TIMED/SABER observation data, the outputs of empirical model/ NRLMSIS2.0 data have been utilized in this dissertation. The NRLMSIS2-0 empirical model, an upgrade from the earlier version, NRLMSISE-00, has become the most recent and popular version of MSIS (Emmert et al., 2020). The NRLMSIS2-0 empirical model data, a substantial revision of the earlier NRLMSISE-00 version, extends from the ground to the exosphere, capturing the mean observed patterns of temperature, and species data files. The NRLMSIS2-0 model is selected to evaluate and validate the performance of the newly developed NN-MLT model and SABER observation. The Community Coordinated Modeling Center (CCMC) and NASA provide their NRLMSIS2.0 model data freely through web: <https://map.nrl.navy.mil/map/pub/nrl/NRLMSIS/NRLMSIS2.0/>.

3.3 Proxy Data

The influence of natural oscillations (QBO, ENSO, and SCO) on the MLT dynamics and variabilities via temperature and ozone parameters have been characterized based on the following proxy data. To examine the contributions of the natural drivers of Quasi-Biennial oscillation (QBO), the proxy data of zonal-mean zonal wind is freely accessed via the website <http://www.geo.fuberlin.de/met/ag/strat/produkte/qbo>. The El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO) data was downloaded from the proxy data of Nino 3.4 via the link: <https://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/data/indices/ersst5.nino.mth.91-20.ascii>. The influence of the solar cycle activity, NASA provides the proxy data of the F10.7 solar radio flux index can be freely retrieved via the website: <https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/form/dx1.html>.

3.4 Analysis Techniques for MLT Dynamics Investigation

In this sub-section, we provided technique details about wavelet analysis to extract periodic oscillations in observational data, the multivariate linear regression (MLR) technique to measure the extent of natural influences on temperature and ozone data and thus construct trends, and the neural network (NN) techniques to develop local model NN-MLT from SABER observational data.

3.4.1 Wavelet analysis Technique

Almost all of the data signals of a system are obtained as a function of time; however, the most distinguished information is hidden in the frequency spectrum of a signal; Therefore, it is

necessary to investigate the signal's frequency to understand the atmospheric dynamics through the atmospheric field of variables temperature and ozone signal at different altitudinal regions of the mesosphere and lower thermosphere region (MLT). Therefore, it needs a transform function, the wavelet, which provides information by decomposing a time series signal into time versus frequency. The wavelet transform is capable of providing such a representation simultaneously (Daubechies, 1992; Torrence and Compo, 1998). This method has been used to obtain frequency components and the time localization of these frequency components. It doesn't mean telling exactly what frequency exists at what time instance, but only what frequency bands exist at what time intervals. The continuous wavelet transform (CWT) function is described in the following, as adapted from Torrence and Compo (1998).

$$W_x^\psi(\tau, s) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|s|}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x(t) * \psi\left(\frac{t-\tau}{s}\right) d(t) \quad (3.1)$$

Where, the transformed signal, $W_x^\psi(\tau, s)$ is a function of two variables, namely, translation, τ , and a scale parameter, s . $\psi\left(\frac{t-\tau}{s}\right)$ is called the mother wavelet and $\psi^*\left(\frac{t-\tau}{s}\right)$ is its complex conjugate. $x(t)$, is the monthly mean temperature and ozone signals of 16-year observation data. The factor $\frac{1}{\sqrt{|s|}}$ is used for energy normalization. Translation, τ , corresponds to time information in the transform domain and is related to the location of the window, as the window is shifted through the signal.

From those different Mother wavelet functions for signal analysis, the Morlet wavelet is an ideal choice (Katsiavrias et al., 2012) because it provides a good balance of temporal and frequency localization. Based on the Heisenberg uncertainty principle, which states that the momentum and the position of a moving particle cannot be estimated simultaneously, the Morlet consistency as a plane wave modulate can be applied to time-frequency localization as well, as follows:

$$\psi_0(\eta) = \pi^{-1/4} e^{i\omega_0\eta} e^{-\eta^2/2} \quad (3.2)$$

Where, $\psi_0(\eta)$, is a wavelet function that depends on a dimensionless time parameter, η , and ω_0 is the dimensionless frequency (with $\omega_0 = 6$) to satisfy the admissibility condition as shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Real part (solid) and imaginary part (dashed) for the Morlet wavelet in the time domain.

Assume that a time series signal, x_n , with equal time spacing δt and $n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$. Torrence and Compo (1998) then derive the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) of the discrete sequence x_n as the convolution of x_n with the scaled and translated version of wavelet $\psi_0(\eta)$:

$$W_n(s) = \sum_{n'=1}^{N-1} x_{n'} \psi^* \left[\frac{(n'-n)\delta t}{s} \right] \quad (3.3)$$

Where $W_n(s)$ is the continuous wavelet transform, * indicates the complex conjugate of the wavelet $\psi_0(\eta)$. By varying the wavelet scale, s , and translating along the localized time index, n , one can construct a picture that shows both the amplitude of any feature(s) versus the scale and how this amplitude varies with time.

The wavelet power spectral (WPS) is also expressed by the square of the wavelet transform, defined as;

$$WPS = [W_n(s)]^2 \quad (3.4)$$

These WPS have been applied to identify (or detect) the significant periodic oscillations of the dynamics and their influence. The overall WPS generates the Global Wavelet Power Spectrum (GWPS), which is used to determine the significant power of periodic oscillations of the dynamics:

$$Gwps = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [W_n(s)]^2 d\tau \quad (3.5)$$

The GWPS is used for producing the power of the temperature and ozone variability as a function of the oscillation frequency (or period).

Whereas the cone of influence shows how the boundary of the data sample affects wavelet coefficients in the wavelet power spectrum. The cone of influence is dealing with finite-length time series, when errors will occur at the beginning and end of the wavelet power spectrum as the Fourier transform assumes the data is cyclic. To overcome this type of issue one solution is to pad the end of the time series with zeroes before doing the wavelet transform and then remove them afterward. The time series is padded with sufficient zeroes to bring the total length N up to the next-higher power of two, thus limiting the edge effects and speeding up the Fourier transform. Padding with zeroes introduces discontinuities at the endpoints and, as one goes to larger scales, decreases the amplitude near the edges as more zeroes enter the analysis. The cone of influence (COI) is the region of the wavelet spectrum in which edge effects become important and is defined here as the e-folding time for the autocorrelation of wavelet power at each scale. For a Morlet wavelet, the e-folding time (τ_s) is $s\sqrt{2}$. Therefore (τ_s) is large at larger scales (larger periods) and forms the vertex of the cone and is small at smaller scales (smaller periods), (τ_s) and forms the base of the cone. This e-folding time is chosen so that the wavelet power for a discontinuity at the edge drops by a factor of e^{-2} and ensures that the edge effects are negligible beyond this point. The size of the COI at each scale also gives a measure of the decorrelation time for a single spike in the time series. The peaks within these regions have presumably been reduced in magnitude due to the zero padding.

An appropriate background spectrum is defined which can be either white noise or red noise and if a peak in the wavelet power spectrum is significantly above this background spectrum, then it can be assumed to be a true feature with a certain percent confidence. It is defined, e.g., significant at the 5% level is equivalent to the 95% confidence level, and implies a test against a certain background level, while the 95% confidence interval refers to the range of confidence about a given value.

3.4.2 Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR) analysis

Wavelet algorithms have been used to diagnose the presence of periodic oscillations (SAO, AO, QBO, ENSO, and SCO) in the temperature and ozone signals to estimate their contributions to the power spectra. Whereas the method of Multivariate Linear Regression analysis (MLR) is applied to determine how much these oscillations affect the atmospheric dynamics based on the field of atmospheric temperature and ozone. This method is adopted from the previous scholars

(Akhil Raj et al., 2018; Kishore et al., 2014; Beig et al., 2012; Hood, 2015; Huang et al., 2014; Randel and Cobb, 1994). The general expression of the multivariate regression model is described here. Let $x(t)$ be a time series of a quantity that is assumed to be represented by one or more independent signals, the simplest assumption is that the relation between $x(t)$ and these processes is linear. Then $x(t)$ can be written as (Von Storch and Zwiers, 2001):

$$x(t_i) = \sum_{k=1}^M a_k y_k(t_i) + r(t_i), \quad (i = 1 \dots N) \quad (3.6)$$

Where a_k are the so-called regression coefficients and y_k are the basis functions representing processes that are believed to play a role in the variability of $x(t_i)$. M is the number of basis functions and N is the length of the time-series. The difference between the calculated quantity (derived from regression coefficients and base functions) and the initially 'observed' quantity is denoted in the residual term $r(t_i)$. Linearity is accounted for regression coefficients a_k and is not necessary for the basis functions. Further details of the theory can be found in Garny (2010). The regression model in this work is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x(z, t) = & a_1(z, t) + \\ & a_2(z, t) \cdot Trend(t) + \\ & \delta(z, t) \cdot Solar(t) + \\ & \beta(z, t) \cdot ENSO(t) + \\ & \gamma(z, t) \cdot QBO(t) \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

where z is an altitude, t is given in a monthly time step, $x(z, t)$ is an estimated ozone volume mixing ratio or temperature measurements at vertical height of z (60-100) and monthly time t , (2005-2020); $a_2(z, t)$, $\delta(z, t)$, $\beta(z, t)$, and $\gamma(z, t)$ are the regression coefficients of the base functions Trend(t), Solar (t), ENSO(t), and QBO(t), respectively. The trend is realized as the least squares linear trend of the time series. Whereas *Solar*(t), *ENSO*(t), and *QBO*(t) are based on the proxy data. To account for the seasonal variability, a Fourier expansion of least squares fitting method (LSF) (Yuan et al., 2006, 2010) is applied to the SABER observations at each altitude throughout the entire 16-year continuous monthly temperature and ozone data set:

$$a_i(z, t) = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^2 A_i \left(\cos \frac{2\pi i}{p_i} (t - \varphi_i) \right) \quad (3.8)$$

Where, $a_i(z, t)$ can be either temperature or ozone, a_0 is a constant value of mean – field, with $i = 1$ and 2 $p_i = 12 \text{ month}/i$, amplitude (A_i) and phase(φ_i) of semi-annual and annual

oscillations of temperature and ozone variation during 2005-2020. Using the above equation, the amplitude and phase of AO and SAO oscillations have been derived.

3.4.3 Gravity wave Potential Energy and Brunt-Vaisala frequency

The MLT region dynamics are not only influenced by atmospheric oscillations (SAO, AO, QBO, ENSO, and SCO) but also its dynamical stability is affected by prevailing atmospheric waves such as gravity waves, tidal waves, and planetary waves. In order to identify the impacts of atmospheric gravity waves on the atmospheric field temperature profiles requires filtering the background atmospheric temperature from the observed. The third-order polynomial fit of the Least Squares has been applied to estimate the background temperature (T_0) from the observation (Ramesh and Sridharan, 2012). Hence, the temperature perturbations are estimated by subtracting the background from the observational data.

$$T_p = T - T_0 \quad (3.9)$$

This perturbed temperature (T_p) is used to estimate the gravity waves potential energy (John and Kumar, 2012). It is generally assumed that temperature profiles of the atmosphere are comprised of a background temperature on which there is an imposed fluctuating component. These temperature fluctuations are thus considered to be reflections of the wave activity at any given height. These fluctuations are extracted and subjected to further analysis to estimate the potential energy of the waves that quantify the wave activity of the region under study. The potential energy of the gravity wave as a function of altitude, z expressed as;

$$E_p(z) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{g(z)}{N(z)} \right)^2 \left(\frac{T_p(z)}{T_0(z)} \right)^2 \quad (3.10)$$

Stability of the atmosphere is characterized based on the Brunt-Vaisala frequency, which is defined as follows:

$$N^2(z) = \frac{g(z)}{T_0(z)} \left(\frac{\partial T_0(z)}{\partial z} + \Gamma_d \right) \quad (3.11)$$

Where g is the acceleration due to gravity, N is the Vaisala frequency oscillation, T_0 is the background temperature, it is estimated based on the third-order polynomial fitting, $\Gamma_d = g/c_p$ is the adiabatic lapse rate, and $c_p = 1004 J K^{-1} kg^{-1}$ is the specific heat capacity of the atmosphere at constant pressure.

Based on this Vaisala frequency, decide whether the MLT atmosphere is stable or not. When N^2 , is statically positive, the atmosphere is stable. Whereas the frequency N^2 , is negative, the atmosphere is unstable, in which the atmospheric lapse rate, $\Gamma = -\frac{\partial T}{\partial z}$ is larger than the adiabatic lapse rate, $\frac{g}{c_p} \approx 9.5 \text{ K km}^{-1}$, the atmosphere is unstable.

3.4.4 Neural Network-based Modeling Techniques

The NN-based modeling technique is an alternative approach to develop models for predicting the mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) variability based on long-term observations.

a) Artificial neural network (NN) Architecture

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) simulate human brain neurons' complex and intricate systems to perform analogous tasks in scientific research graphical representation is shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Human brain and scientific neural network layers with the activation function.

These neural networks are extensively interconnected in a parallel network system consisting of input, hidden, and output layers, enable to handle highly nonlinear and complex problems. These networks' building blocks of input layers supply data to the network, output layers generate

appropriate responses to the inputs, and one or more intermediate layers (hidden layers) serve as assemblies of characteristic identifiers, each containing one or more neurons (Figure 3.5). The concepts of the NN modeling technique as a mathematical computation tool were first established by McCulloch et al. (1943), while the learning capacity of neural networks was enhanced by Widrow and Hoff (1960) by modifying the network's weight and bias. These weights and biases dictate the input-output relationship in neural network modeling techniques. Rumelhart et al. (1986) introduced a backpropagation error algorithm to increase the ability of neural network computing to solve nonlinear input-output relationships in feed-forward neural networks.

(a) Weighted input neurons in an activation function

(b) Three nonlinear activation functions

Figure 3.5: The architecture layers of a feed-forward artificial neural network (ANN) are illustrated with (a) the weighted input neuron layers passing through an activation function and (b) the three common nonlinear activation functions (sigmoid, tanh, and ReLU) along with their respective scales (Eichie et al., 2017).

The transfer function expresses the weighted input neurons that feed to the input layer in the process of feed-forward propagation. The input signals $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ belong to the input neuron, which is represented by a vector x . Each input signal, on the other hand, is interconnected by a corresponding weight.

$w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_i$.

$$w_1x_1 + w_2x_2 + w_3x_3 + \dots + w_ix_n \quad (3.12)$$

The weighted net input (sum of input) signal is then passed through the activation function (sigmoid, tanh, and ReLU) in hidden layers as shown in Figure 3.5 and is used to change the linearity into nonlinearity to solve complex phenomena. In which the hyperbolic tangent sigmoid activation function is utilized for the hidden neurons, and then the output signals of the node are computed in the basic algebraic equation as follows:

$$y_i = \varphi(\sum_{i=1}^n w_ix_i + b_i) \quad (3.13)$$

Where; y_i is the output signal of neuron i ; b_i , is the bias associated with neuron i ; and φ is the activation function. The hyperbolic tangent sigmoid activation function, represented as $\tanh(\cdot)$, is given by:

$$\varphi = \tanh(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}} = \frac{2}{1 + e^{-2x}} - 1 \quad (3.14)$$

The tanh function φ is often employed to constrain the output values between -1 and 1 for input values extending from negative to positive infinity. After all the data processing in the hidden layer using the network's activation function, the output may have high weights; it returns to the input layers in the backpropagation process from the output via a hidden layer to adjust the weights or biases. Backpropagation in neural networks is utilized to update the weights by minimizing the error between the model output and observed values, ultimately leading to improved performance in Bayesian regularization. The Bayesian regularization algorithm is chosen over the conventional backpropagation method and offers various benefits for training (or modeling) neural networks (Burden and Winkler, 2009). As noted by researchers such as Foresee and Martin (1997), MacKay (1992), and Okoh et al. (2018), the Bayesian regularization algorithm is employed alongside backpropagation to adjust the weights during network training as demonstrated in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Flow of a feed-forward neural network utilizing an error backpropagation method (adapted with permission from Sai Gowtam and Tulasi Ram, 2017).

b) Neural Network training:

The objective of the neural networks is to develop a model that can predict the temperature of the MLT region. A dataset is selected to train the model in the MLT regions at 60, 75, and 90 km. Five known input variables, including universal time (UT), latitude, longitude, F10.7 solar flux, and ozone volume mixing ratio, are utilized in the training process for developing the MLT temperature model.

Figure 3.7: Variations in mean square error (MSE) during the neural network (NN) training process, showing the performance of the model at each stage of training iterations (epochs) and the predictability of the network at the convergence point.

A total of fifteen years of SABER observation data (from 2006 to 2020) is utilized and split into two datasets for training and testing the model. In this analysis, the training dataset comprises approximately 90% of the total observation data from January 01, 2006, to December 31, 2019, while the remaining 10% of data from January 01, 2020, to December 31, 2020, is employed for testing. After conducting multiple tests, it was determined that two hidden layers of neurons (7 and 8) and one suitable output provided the best results to construct the model NN-MLT. This followed a procedure similar to those adopted by previous investigators ([Hecht-Nielsen, 1988](#); [Blum, 1992](#); [Berry and Linoff, 1997](#)). The choice of neurons in the input-output layers is a problem-oriented activity. After developing the model through network training, it can be evaluated, and predictions can be made using the testing dataset. Furthermore, Figure 3.7 demonstrates how the NN-based model works at each stage of the training iterations (epochs) and shows the network's predictability within the convergence point via the mean square error loss function. The testing dataset is independent and not used during training but serves to assess the network model's predictive performance using various statistical techniques, includes mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), standard deviation (σ), and correlation coefficient (R) analysis. The NN-based model works at each stage of the training iterations (epochs) which shows the network's predictability within the convergence point via the mean square error loss function.

CHAPTER FOUR

4. Long-term MLT Temperature and ozone variability and its response to natural drivers using 16 years (2005–2020) of TIMED/SABER Observation over low latitude 3–15⁰N

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4.1 Introduction

The mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) is a sensitive region of the Earth's middle and upper atmosphere located in the range from 60 to 100 km altitude, interacts with the lower and upper atmospheric climate systems, and plays a significant role in energetic and dynamical investigations. The MLT, which acts as a natural laboratory for the study of dynamic processes, is home to a variety of atmospheric phenomena, which could be characterized by the main parameters of temperature and ozone. To characterize the dynamics of the middle and upper atmosphere, various oscillations in long-term temperature and ozone have been identified. Among them, seasonal oscillations (SAO and AO) are well-known atmospheric influences in the equatorial regions and are major sources of intra-annual variations (Yue et al., 2019; Ern et al., 2015). In addition to the seasonal oscillations, including natural influences like quasi-Biennial oscillation (QBO), El Nino-Southern Oscillation (ENSO), and solar cycle (SC) has become crucial to accurately understand the long-term variations and tendencies in the middle atmospheric dynamics (Kishore et al., 2014; Li et al., 2013).

Numerous previous studies have been conducted on the middle and upper atmospheric regions influenced by seasonal oscillations or natural drivers over the mid and high latitudes (Das, 2021; She et al., 2019). Temperature and ozone seasonal variations in the stratosphere and mesosphere have been observed by (Joshi et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2007; Offer Mann et al., 2004; Espy and Stegman, 2002; States and Gardner, 2000). The response of long-term temperature or ozone variability to natural influences in the stratosphere and mesosphere is reported elsewhere (Randel

et al., 2009; Huang et al., 2006). Particularly, QBO and ENSO influences on the middle atmospheric temperature is studied by (Li et al., 2008, Li et al., 2013; Domeisen et al., 2018) and for ozone by (Olsen et al., 2019). In addition to the quasi-Biennial and El Niño-Southern Oscillations, the 11-year solar activity is also a significant source of the inter-annual variability in the mesosphere region (Bordi et al., 2015; Fadnavis et al., 2012; Beig et al., 2008; Offermann et al., 2010).

Apart from the mid and high latitudes a number of studies have been reported in low-latitudes by considering seasonal oscillations or natural influences while constructing long-term variabilities or trends in the mesosphere (Kishore et al., 2014; Nath and Sridharan, 2014). The long-term seasonal oscillation and natural influences of atmospheric variability and their dynamics have been revealed in measurements (ground and space-based) and model simulations. Some modelling studies have focused on mesospheric regions (Ramesh et al., 2020; Beig et al., 2012; Argall et al., 2007; Khosravi, 2002). Both ground-based and satellite-based observations were useful in determining the middle atmospheric variability. For instance, a number of ground-based observations have been used to investigate variability in the middle atmosphere (Kishore et al., 2014; She et al., 2009; Keckhut et al., 1995). From Rayleigh lidar measurements, (Keckhut et al., 1995), they observed a long-term cooling trend of 0.4 K/year in the mesosphere at 44⁰N. Of course, ground-based measurements may not be efficient due to saturation in the upper atmosphere (Remsberg et al., 2002; She et al., 2009). In contrast, satellite observations provide regional and global coverage in the MLT region. In recent, SABER temperature and ozone data were widely used to investigate the thermal structure and dominant dynamical processes in the MLT region (Huang et al., 2006; Huang et al., 2014; Dikty et al., 2010; Gan et al., 2012). By improving the data quality in the latest versions, there has been an adequate number of studies on long-term variabilities and trends in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) (Das, 2021; Huang and Mayr, 2019; Gan et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2016).

Most of the former studies on MLT considered a single parameter (either temperature or ozone) in investigating the variability and trends over mid and high latitudes, however, there is a sparse report over low latitudes, which are driving force to choose the current study. The main aim of this chapter is to investigate the long-term MLT temperature and ozone variability, natural influences, and tendencies taking into account the intra-annual (SAO and AO) and inter-annual (ENSO, QBO, and SC) variations from proxy data using a robust technique of wavelet analysis

and Multi variant linear regression analysis (MLR) using 16 years (2005-2020) of TIMED/SABER observational data in the northern low latitudes (3-15⁰ N). The selected data period (2005- 2020) covers one solar cycle, which is 24 and continues into the beginning of solar cycle 25. The purpose of our investigations serves to verify the accuracy of numerical models in order to forecast. The outlines are organized as follows: Section 4.2 describes the dataset and data analysis process. The long-term monthly mean temperature and ozone variability and their responses to ENSO, QBO, and SC in the SABER observation are reported in Section 4.3. The results are summarized in Section 4.4 with conclusions.

4.2 Data and analysis Methods

SABER data

Details of the SABER instrument and data retrieval mechanism are provided elsewhere in Chapter 3, Section 3.1. In this chapter, we used 16 years (2005–2020) of SABER temperature and ozone data over the MLT region downloaded from the website: <http://saber.gats-inc.com/index.php>. In addition to TIMED/SABER data, we employed proxy data sets to validate the background impacts in order to explore long-term variations and trends.

Wavelet Analysis

In this study we applied robust wavelet analysis technique to extract/detect/identify dominant modes of MLT oscillations (AO, SAO, QBO, ENSO, and SC) in the ozone and temperature data over low-latitude region. The detailed methodology has already been presented in chapter 3 section 3.4.1

Multivariate linear regression (MLR) analysis

Multivariate linear regression analysis is performed on the long-term monthly mean temperature and ozone signals to distinguish the effects of intra-annual (annual and semiannual) and inter-annual (QBO, ENSO, and SC) variations of the proxy data using a least-squares technique to fit signals from 16 years of data (January 2005 to December 2020) in the MLT altitude range of 60–100 km at low latitude.

4.2 Result and Discussion

In this section, 16 years of long-term SABER temperature and ozone observation data is used in the height range of 60–100 km of MLT region. The monthly mean and composite annual temperature and ozone profiles in the height range of 60-100 km over the low-latitude band of 3-

15° N were used to generate the contour plots as shown in Figure 4.1(a-d) to study long-term MLT variability. The upper panel of Figure 4.1(a-b) indicates the contour of monthly mean and composite annual temperature variations; the lower panel of Figure 4.1(c-d) represents the monthly mean and composite annual ozone variability. From Figure 4.1(a and b), a maximum monthly mean temperatures clearly observed from 200–240 k in the height range of 60–70 km and a minimum temperature range of 166–190 k at a height range of about 90–100 km. Figure 4.1(b), which is composite-annual temperature, shows maximum temperature variability (200–240 K) in the height range of 60–70 km, with the minimum temperature declining to around 160–180 K at a height range of about 95–100 km. Furthermore, we also observe annual oscillation (AO) in the lower MLT, with a peak around June/July, and semiannual oscillation (SAO) in the upper MLT, with peaks in March/April and again in September/October. A cold spot is clearly visible around 75 km in the equinox period (March/April) with a temperature of 170 K and it is immediately followed by a warm spot from 80-85 km with a temperature of 215 K. Such a phenomenon is assumed to be the result of the Mesospheric temperature inversion (MTI).

Figure 4.1: Monthly and Composite-annual mean of temperature and ozone variation based on SABER observations during 2005 to 2020 in the height range of 60–100 km.

The lower panel of Figure 4.1(c and d) show the monthly mean and composite-annual ozone of long-term variability. The monthly mean OVMR (ozone volume mixing ratio) at heights below

85 km is fairly low (about 3 ppmv), but above 85 km it rises from 6-12 ppmv. Whereas Figure 4.1(d) shows the composite annual OVMR (ozone volume mixing ratio) variability with peak values in the range of 8-10 ppmv at upper MLT (90-100 km) around March-May and September-November. At altitudes below 90 km, the composite OVMR concentrations are very low, with variability ranging from 0.2 ppmv to 3 ppmv. Moreover, the SAO was observed with a peak value of 11.2 ppmv in February and 10.66 ppmv in May in the upper MLT (85-100 km), along with the annual oscillations (AO) in the lower MLT around July. Our findings are in good agreement with prior research (Nath and Sridharan, 2014), especially in the upper MLT (85-100 km), although agreement in the lower MLT (60-70 km) is modest. We suspect that the disparities between our results and those of (Nath and Sridharan, 2014; kishor et al., 2014) for ozone and temperature at higher altitudes are related. In general, the composite annual temperature and ozone variability have exhibited less variability than the monthly mean temperature and ozone variability.

4.2.1 The Periodicity of MLT Temperature and Ozone Variations

In this section, we extract dominant periodic oscillations such as SAO (semiannual oscillation), AO (annual oscillation), QBO (quasi Biennial oscillation), ENSO (El Niño Southern Oscillation), and solar cycle (SC) by applying the robust technique of continuous wavelet transform (CWT) on monthly mean MLT temperature and ozone data. Figures 4.2 and 4.3 depict the contour plots of CWT along with the global power spectrum of temperature and ozone data at every 10 km interval from 60-100 km.

Figure 4.2 depicts the monthly mean temperature oscillations and their power in five vertical zones at (60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 km), with emphasis on the dominant annual and semiannual oscillations. We have clearly shown that inter annual oscillations AO and SAO are dominant at all MLT levels (60-100km) and have low amplitudes at certain heights. AO is dominant at all height levels except weak amplitude at 90 and 100 km, whereas SAO is present at all heights except weak amplitudes at 60 km. In addition to intra-seasonal oscillations, long-term oscillations are also identified (QBO and ENSO). QBO (28-32 months) is presented at all heights over the entire period (2006-2018) with varying amplitudes except at 90km. ENSO (52-64) is presented at all heights with varying amplitudes, except at 90 km during the study period 2009-2015.

Figure 4. 2: (a) Monthly mean temperature time series from January 2005 to December 2020 at 10 km intervals ranging from 60-100 km. (b) The contour is the wavelet power spectrum with the COI (con of influence). (c) The global wavelet power spectrum (blue line). The dashed red line is the 95% confidence level (5% significance level) for the global wavelet spectrum. (d) Scale-average wavelet power over the 4-8 month band for the monthly temperature. The dashed line is the 95% confidence level (*significant at the 5% level*).

Figure 4.3: (a) Monthly mean ozone time series from January 2005 to December 2020 at 10 km intervals ranging from 60-100 km. (b) The contour is the wavelet power spectrum with the COI (con of influence). (c) The global wavelet power spectrum (blue line). The dashed red line is the 95% confidence level (5% significance level) for the global wavelet spectrum. (d) Scale-average wavelet power over the 4-8 month band for the monthly temperature. The dashed line is the 95% confidence level (*significant at the 5% level*).

Whereas ozone has dominant intra-seasonal oscillations of AO and SAO at all height levels in Figure 4.3 below. SAO is dominant at all heights except with varying amplitudes at (60 & 70) km, however AO is present at all heights with less significant at upper MLT heights of 90 & 100 km. Long-term oscillation QBO signature is present at all heights with weak amplitudes at the upper MLT (80-100km). The ENSO signal is presented at all heights with varying amplitudes during the entire study period (2008–2016). Our results are consistent with recent long-term studies (Zhang et al., 2017; Sharma et al., 2016) on upper MLT heights (at 80, 90, and 100 km).

4.2.2 Semiannual and Annual Variations in MLT Temperature and Ozone variability

The Multivariate Regression Model, which contains the main functions representing the natural oscillations such as solar cycle activity (SC), the El Nino–Southern Oscillation (ENSO), and the quasi-Biennial oscillation (QBO), is employed to construct the MLT variability and trends. In addition to the long-term natural periodic oscillations, the semiannual and annual oscillations also contribute to the dynamics of MLT temperature and ozone variability. Annual and semi-annual oscillations in the lower atmosphere have been studied for many years (Ern et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2017). (Ratnam et al., 2008) investigated the relationship between low-latitude MLT SAO and stratospheric QBO. However, there were a few reports on MLT oscillations particularly in height range of 60–100 km (Zhang et al., 2017; Nath et al., 2014; Kishore et al., 2014). In this section, SAO and AO oscillations in MLT temperature and ozone signals are analyzed at an altitude range of 60 to 100 km. The amplitudes, A_i , and phases, f_i ($i = 1 \& 2$) of temperature and ozone are shown in Figures 4.4 and 4.5 during the period 2005–2020. The amplitude of semiannual and annual oscillations in temperature and ozone data are shown in Figure 4.4(a-d). The amplitude of SAO and AO in temperature are shown in the first panel of Figure 4.4 (a and b). From 2006 to 2016, the amplitude of SAO exhibits a downward phase propagation, but the amplitude of AO propagates downwards with weak amplitudes throughout the study period. In the second panel of Figure 4.4(c and d), it displays the amplitudes of SAO and AO in ozone. AO and SAO amplitudes are significant below 70 km for all years except the period 2010-2012, when a maximum amplitude is observed and even continues to upper MLT heights. The significant amplitude of semiannual and annual oscillations in the temperature and ozone volume mixing ratio during the period from 2010 to 2012 in the height region of 60–100 km is found due to an intensive F10.7 solar radio flux, which is the period of solar maximum.

However, a major contribution from solar influences was found in the temperature variability when compared to ozone volume mixing ratio in the MLT region.

Figure 4.4: Amplitudes of semiannual and annual oscillations of mesospheric temperature (upper panel, a-b) and ozone volume mixing ratio (lower panel, c-d) respectively, as a function of height for the period from January 2005 to 2020 December.

We construct the vertical profile of amplitudes of AO and SAO from 60-100 km region as shown in Figure 4.5(a-d) with the corresponding phase in Figure 4.5(e-h). The vertical distribution of SAO in temperature (Figure 4.5 a and e) reveals a maximum amplitude of 7 k at a height of 85 km, along with a corresponding maximum phase of oscillation of 6 months at 89 km. whereas for (Figure 4.5 b and f) maximum amplitude, 4 k of AO is observed at a height of 77 km, along with a maximum phase of 12 months at 95 km. The amplitudes of SAO and AO in temperature show a maximum just below and above 80 km in the MLT. The effect of climate change is expected to be more apparent at higher elevations as the amplitude of temperature and ozone changes rises with height due to the decrease in density. This amplitude of SAO and AO in temperature variability may also associated with El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO), and the Quasi-Biennial Oscillation (QBO). The study of (Nath and Sridharan 2014) also found a good agreements on the amplitude of SAO and AO in MLT temperature from SABER observations.

Figure 4.5: The amplitude (top) and phase (bottom) of the SAO and AO plots of temperature and ozone variations as a function of height (60 to 100 km) for the period from January 2005 to December 2020 in terms of month.

Similarly, the amplitude and phase of SAO & AO oscillations in the ozone volume mixing ratio are presented in Figure 4.5(c, d, g, and h). The ozone volume mixing ratio of AO and SAO has a maximum amplitude of 0.43 ppmv at 98 km and 1.02 ppmv at 94 km, with a corresponding maximum phase of oscillation of 5.5 months at 80 km and 12 months at 89 km. Amplitudes of SAO and AO in OVMR show significant enhancement above 80 km and 90 km, respectively. It is worth mentioning that the observed amplitude and phase profiles are in good agreement with the previous satellite observations (Xu et al., 2007). In our observation we have shown, the semiannual oscillations of temperature and ozone in the MLT are highly significant when compared to the annual oscillations of temperature and ozone. Similarly, (Nath and Sridharan, 2014) observed oscillations in the long term middle atmospheric temperature and ozone variability where they found semi-annual oscillation (SAO) is predominant in the lower stratosphere and upper mesosphere. In general, the MLT temperature has been highly disturbed in the amplitudes of SAO and AO compared with the ozone volume mixing ratio. Apart from annual and semiannual oscillations, long-term natural influences are characterized using the proxy data of QBO, ENSO, and the 11-year solar cycle in the MLT region. As the temperature

variation is expected to contain natural periodic signals, like the QBO, ENSO and 11 years SC (Randel and Cobb, 1994).

4.2.3 MLT Temperature and Ozone Responses to Natural Influences

In this section, the natural influences of QBO (period of ~28 months), and ENSO (period of ~60 months), and SC (~11 years) in the long-term temperature and ozone variability is investigated. The reference time series of solar activity is the 11-year solar radio flux at 10.7 cm (F10.7) shown in Figure 4.6 (a) solar flux units (sfu), where $1 \text{ sfu} = 10^{-22} \text{ W.m}^{-2}\text{Hz}$ (Tapping, 2013). The Nino 3.4 index, displayed in Figure 4.6 (b), is the reference time series for the El Nino Southern Oscillation (ENSO) (Li et al., 2013). As illustrated in Figure 4.6(c) (Baldwin et al., 2001), the reference time series of the Quasi Biennial Oscillation (QBO) at 30 hPa is the zonal-mean zonal wind at the equator. By using these proxy data sets, multiple linear regression analysis is applied on temperature and ozone to examine the contributions of the natural influences (QBO at 30 hPa, ENSO, and SC) in MLT regions (60-100 k) for the period of 2005 to 2020 as shown in Figures (4.7, 4.8, 4.9, & 4.10).

Figure 4 6: Reference time series on the monthly basis from January 2005 to June 2020 for 16 years used for the regression analyses. (a) Solar radio flux at 10.7 cm (F10.7) to characterize the solar cycle (b) Nino 3.4 Index to characterize the ENSO signal (c) 30 hPa zonal winds over the equator to characterize the QBO.

Figure 4.7(a-c) shows the MLT temperature and ozone response to F10.7, ENSO, and QBO drivers for the period 2005 to 2020 at each altitudinal region in a 10 km interval between 60 and 100 km. In Figure 4.7(a) column-wise, the blue legend indicates the temperature response and red indicates ozone response to F10.7, further it clearly visible influence is dominant around during 2011 to 2015 compared to remaining period due to high solar activity. The positive and negative effects of F10.7 solar radio flux on ozone and temperature is found, respectively, in the lower MLT (60, 70, and 80 km) and vice versa in the upper MLT (80, 90, and 100 km). Hence, we conclude that F10.7 solar radio flux has a substantial impact on upper MLT temperature in comparison with ozone variability. Both (Li et al., 2011 and Beig et al., 2012) discovered a substantial results of F10.7 impacts on temperature variability at various places and periods, with similar results to ours. Moreover our observations of a strong SC impacts on MLT temperature is in agreement with the result obtained by (Fadnavis et al., 2009). A similar work in HALOE observations was reported by (Fadnavis et al., 2012) who revealed the significant temperature response to solar variability in the 0–30⁰N latitude bands and reported a positive response in the upper stratosphere and mesosphere regions.

Figure 4.7: The temperature and ozone response to (a) F10.7, (b) ENSO and (c) QBO at every 10 km intervals from 60 to 100 km. Blue legend indicates the temperature response and red indicates ozone response to natural influences.

In addition to that of F10.7 solar radio flux, ENSO and QBO enhance the temperature and ozone variability at low latitudes in the mesosphere (Li et al., 2013). The quasi-Biennial and El Niño-Southern oscillations are well-known dominant modes of tropical tropospheric and stratospheric variability (Gao et al., 2017; Calvo et al., 2010; Simpson et al., 2011). Although further studies are needed to quantify the presence of ENSO and QBO influences on atmospheric temperature and ozone in the MLT region, their presence has been demonstrated in Figure 4.7(b and c). As shown in Figure 4.7(b), the impacts of ENSO on the MLT temperature and ozone are presented, in which the temperature and ozone response to ENSO are quite opposite to each other at all MLT heights till the year 2011/2012 and afterward, vice-versa. This implies the time from 2005 to 2011/2012, for a period of 60 months, significant/positive temperature and insignificant/negative ozone responses to ENSO appeared above the height of 70 km, whereas

below 70 km, the response is the reverse. However, after the period of 2011/2012, insignificant/negative temperature and significant/ positive ozone responses to ENSO existed from the height of 70 km up to 100 km, while below 70 km, the situation associated with ENSO periods has been reversed. According to our observations, the MLT temperature and ozone variability are enhanced during ENSO, QBO, and SC events. Our analysis reveals that during an ENSO event, the MLT temperature and ozone variability are similarly enhanced. At all MLT levels except 80 km, the temperature and ozone responses to QBO are out of phase, which clearly incidence from Figure 4.7(c). Using model data, (Garcia-Herrera et al., 2006) reported that a significant ENSO phenomenon had been revealed in the middle atmospheric region. Similarly, (Huang et al., 2008) have been reported with evidence that the temperature and ozone variability are out of phase in the height range of 30–80 km. Our conclusion at 80 km, the temperature and ozone response is in phase to all natural influences (F10.7, ENSO, & QBO), and are out of phase below and above 80 km. Finally, the overall magnitude of the temperature response is greater than the ozone.

Figure 4.8: Contour of monthly mean temperature and ozone variability response to (a-b) F10.7 solar activity (c-d) ENSO (e-f) QBO during a 16-year period, as a function of altitude and time, using the SABER data set.

From 2005 to 2020, Figure 4.8(a-f) depicts contours as a function of altitude and time, indicating temperature and ozone variability in the MLT region due to natural influences such as F10.7 solar radio flux, ENSO, and QBO. Positive values indicate that responses are larger and they appear in brown, red, and yellow, whereas negative responses are represented in green and blue colors. In Figure 4.8(a and b), we have shown the significant temperature and ozone responses to the dominant F10.7 solar radio flux in all altitude ranges from 60 to 100 km, during the period from 2010 to 2016. Moreover, for temperature, a significant positive response is observed at upper MLT levels and a negative response is visible at lower MLT levels, whereas the reverse is true for ozone influence. Similarly, (Huang et al., 2016) found that the ozone and temperature responses are both positive over the range of altitudes from 80 to 100 km (upper MLT) over the low-latitudes. Whereas, the ozone and temperature responses are negatively correlated (out of phase) throughout the lower MLT between 50 and 80 km. In addition to the natural influence of F10.7 solar radio flux, both the influence of the El Niño–Southern Oscillation and the quasi-Biennial on MLT temperature and ozone variability have been identified in Figure 4.8(c-d, and e-f). Until 2012, ENSO had a positive influence on the lower MLT and a negative influence on the upper MLT temperature; after 2012, the reverse is true, whereas ozone is completely out of phase with temperature observations. Our results are in relatively good agreement with those of the ENSO signature in the MLT predicted by numerical model studies (Li et al., 2008; Sassi et al., 2004; Garcia-Herrera et al., 2006). The positive influence occurred during the warm El Nio phase of (wENSO) and the negative influence happened during the cold La Nia phase of (cENSO) in the atmospheric temperature variability reported by (Huang et al., 2019). On the contrary, during wENSO (cENSO), our results show a diminution (rise) in ozone mixing ratios. The other prominent tropical variability, the quasi Biennial Oscillation (QBO), as well, we can clearly observe the out of phase influences between temperature and ozone variability. Generally, for three influences, the magnitude of temperature responses varies from -1.4 to 2.5 K, whereas for ozone it ranges from -0.1 to 0.35 ppmv, which is relatively low. Around 80km, both the natural influences and parameters are in phase, which strengthens the previous results. Figure 4.9 shows the vertical distribution of the climatological mean temperature and ozone in the natural drivers (F10.7, ENSO, and QBO) as a function of height from 60 to 100 km. It shows the positive and negative responses of temperature and ozone at different altitude levels. In Figure 4.9(a and d), the negatively temperature and ozone response to F10.7 occurred in the

lower MLT (60-80) km, and above 80 km it responds positively with a maximum value of 2.8 K in temperature & 0.7 ppmv in ozone. In a similar manner, (Li et al., 2008; Kishor et al., 2014; Nath and Sridharan 2014) reported the temperature and ozone variability associated with the 11-year solar cycle, ENSO, & the QBO using ground and satellite based measurements.

Figure 4.9: The temperature and ozone responses to the F10.7 solar flux, ENSO, and QBO as a function of altitude (60-100 km) computed from the mean of 16-year SABER observational data.

A most recent study (Gan et al., 2017) reported the temperature response to SC activity based on the 2002–2015 SABER observations in the upper MLT, and its maximum response value exceeds ~2.0 and ~4.0 K/100 sfu at around 85 and 100 km, respectively. (Fadnavis and Beig 2006) also found a non-significant OVMR response to SC below 75 km and a positive response at 80 km. Whereas, (Li et al., 2008 and 2013) observed a large positive ENSO response in the mesosphere, which has been observed in both SABER temperature and whole-atmosphere community climate model (WACCM) simulations, with an anomalous warming of 1.0 K/MEI (Multivariate ENSO Index) in the tropics. Here, the vertical distribution of ENSOs impact on temperature and ozone variability is depicted in Figure 4.9(b and e) along with altitude increase. In the present study, we have also found the minimum peak temperature response at 70 & 85 km

with values (-0.8 K & 0.65 K) and the maximum peak response at 75 & 90-95 km with (0.7 & 0.65 K) whereas in ozone their minimum peaks at 73, 82, & 96 km with amplitudes of -0.035, -0.06, & -0.04 ppmv and maximum peaks at 78 & 90 km with amplitudes of 0.01 & 0.07ppmv is presented. The QBO influence on temperature and ozone is shown in Figure 4.9(c and f); it also exhibits alternative positive and negative responses like ENSO. Temperature shows minimum responses at 82 and 95 km with amplitudes of -0.37 & -0.35 m/s, whereas maximum peaks are at 73 & 87 km with 0.3 and 0.28 m/s. For ozone, a constant slight positive response is observed at the lower MLT after 85 km. It behaves as a negative response with a minimum peak at ~93 km with -0.07 m/s amplitude. Similarly, (Nath and Sridharan 2014) also found a positive temperature response to ENSO in the height range of 80-90 km, peaking at 85 km (0.56 K/SOI). In contrast to our results, (Nath and Sridharan 2014) found the ozone response to QBO is insignificant in the height range of 50–80 km, whereas the response shows a small positive maximum at 98 km (upper MLT). In general, among three natural influences, the F10.7 impacts strongly positive in the upper-MLT and negatively in the lower-MLT in both temperature and ozone, whereas ENSO and QBO influence alternatively in the MLT over the equatorial region.

4.2.4 Variations of long-term MLT Temperature and Ozone Trends

Temperature and ozone variability were investigated through long-term trend analyses. We applied MLR analysis by considering oscillations and natural influences to construct the long-term trends of MLT temperature and ozone. In the current study, at heights ranging from 60 to 100 km, the MLT temperature and ozone trends have shown apparent negative and positive values by considering the natural events.

Figure 4.10: Trends of MLT temperature and ozone as a function of altitude over the periods of 2005–2020.

Figure 4.10(a) depicts a distinct cooling trend (negative values) in the range of $\sim 0-0.85$ K/decade of temperature in the lower MLT (60-75 km) region, followed by a warming trend (positive values) in the range of $\sim 0-1.25$ K/decade in the upper MLT (85-100 km), which is bridged by a near-zero trend in the middle MLT (75-85 km). Figure 4.10 (b) shows that ozone has a consistent cooling (negative) trend of ~ 0.12 ppmv/decade in the lower and middle MLT (60–85 km) region, before changing to warming (positive) trend peaks around ~ 0.27 ppmv/decade at 94 km. Our results are similar to those in the previous reported work (Ramesh and Sridharan., 2018; Li et al., 2008; Kishor et al., 2014; Nath and Sridharan 2014) on temperature and ozone variability in the range between 15 and 100 km height associated with the 11-year solar cycle, ENSO, and the QBO using ground and satellite-based measurements. Particularly, (Kishor et al., 2014) found a similar cooling (negative) temperature trend in the (60–75 km) height range and a warming (positive) trend above 75 km over the low latitudes of Gadanki and Reunion. The study of (Nath and Sridharan 2014) also found a constant trend at zero value in the ozone volume mixing ratio in the lower MLT region (60-80 km) from SABER measurements. Recently (Ramesh and Sridharan, 2018) reported a warming trend above 84 km with a maximum value of 0.6-0.7 K/day/decade in the mesopause region between (90–100 km) based on SABER temperature observation data over the low latitude region. In addition to natural events, greenhouse gas concentrations may induce cooling (negative) and warming (positive) trends in the lower and upper MLT temperatures and ozone variability.

4.2.5 Summary and Conclusions

This chapter has presented the temperature and ozone variability based on 16 years (2005 to 2020) of monthly mean SABER observations in the height range of 60–100 km over the low latitude region of $3-15^{\circ}$ N. The MLR method is applied to investigate the long-term temperature and ozone responses to natural drivers (SC, ENSO, and QBO) as well as their trends. Natural influences appear to be the primary drivers of the MLT temperature and ozone variability. The results and conclusions drawn from our observational analysis are furnished as follows:

1. The composite-annual contour temperature from (2005 to 2020) depicts annual oscillation (AO) in the lower MLT with a peak around June/July and semiannual oscillation (SAO) in the upper MLT with peaks around March/April and again in September/October. A cold spot is clearly visible around 75 km in the equinox period (March/April) with the temperature of 170 K and it is immediately followed by a warm spot from 80-85km with a temperature of

215 K. Such a phenomenon is assumed to be the result of Mesospheric Temperature Inversion (MTI). Whereas, for ozone, SAO is observed with a peak around February (11.2 ppmv) and again in May (10.66 ppmv) in the upper MLT (85-100 km), along with the annual oscillations in the lower MLT having a peak around July.

2. Using the wavelet analysis technique on temperature data, dominant intra-seasonal oscillations (AO & SAO) and long term oscillations (QBO& ENSO) are identified. The inter-annual oscillations AO and SAO are dominant at all MLT levels (60-100km) and have low amplitudes at certain heights. Long term oscillations show their presence with varying amplitudes in entire study period except at 90km. whereas ozone has dominant intra-seasonal oscillations of AO and SAO at all height levels. SAO is dominant at all heights except with varying amplitudes at 60 and 70 km, whereas AO is present at all heights with less significant at upper MLT heights of 90 and 100 km. Long-term oscillations (QBO and ENSO) signatures are presented at all heights with varying amplitudes during the entire study period especially, QBO possess weak amplitudes at the upper MLT (80-100km).
3. To examine the contributions of the natural drivers/influences (QBO at 30 hPa, ENSO, and SC events) on the MLT temperature and ozone variability, the proxy data zonal wind, Nino 3.4, and F10.7 solar flux index are used. The temperature and ozone response to F10.7 are opposite to each other and vice-versa at the lower (60, 70, and 80 km) and upper (80, 90, and 100 km) MLT. At 80 km, the temperature and ozone respond in phase to all natural influences (F10.7, ENSO, and QBO), and are out of phase below and above 80 km. The magnitude of the temperature response is greater than the ozone at all heights.
4. The distribution of the climatological mean temperature and ozone in the natural influences (F10.7, ENSO, and QBO) is shown as a function of height from 60-100. The positive impacts of F10.7 solar flux on the upper MLT temperature and ozone (2.8 K and 0.7 ppmv) and its impact negatively in the lower MLT region (-2.0 K & 0.45 ppmv), whereas the impacts of ENSO and QBO on the MLT in opposite directions over the equatorial region.
5. The long-term trends of MLT temperature and ozone is constructed under the natural drivers based on the MLR analysis. Both the temperature and the ozone reveal cooling trends (-0.85 K/decade & -0.12 ppmv/decade) in the lower MLT (60-80 km) and are followed by the upper MLT (85-100 km) warming trends (1.25 K/decade & 0.27 ppmv/decade) over the low latitude.

CHAPTER FIVE

5. The Role of Gravity Wave in the Mesosphere-Lower Thermosphere Inversions over low latitude (3-15°N)

The contents of work presented in this chapter is submitted to the journal of *Atmospheric chemistry and physics (EGU) Research* by the author's Lingerew, C., and Jaya Prakash Raju, U.

5.1 Introduction

The mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) dynamic regions act as a transition zone between the lower and upper atmosphere, which underlies atmospheric wave processes (tidal waves, planetary waves, and gravity waves). It is a well-known fact that atmospheric waves, especially gravity waves (GWs) generated from the lower atmosphere, propagate into the middle and upper atmosphere and break in the MLT region during propagation and dissipate their energy and momentum into the background atmosphere, influencing the dynamics of the MLT thermal structure, global atmospheric circulation, variability and even the MIL phenomenon (Lindzen, (1981) and Holton, (1983)). The Mesospheric Inversion Layer (MIL) is a feature of the MLT region in the temperature profile. The MIL is a symptom (sign) of wave saturation in the mesosphere because the temperature inversion occurs at altitudes when the lapse rate is less than half of the dry adiabatic lapse rate (Sica et al. (2007)). Temperature inversions has been omnipresent features in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere regions for decades, and they have been comprehensively studied in the past by using all sorts of available techniques (e.g., lidar, radar, rocket sonde, and satellite) over different geographic locations.

Because of gravity waves (GWs) momentum and energy deposition, it is thought to be the principal mechanism driving large-scale circulation and coupling of distinct atmospheric layers, as well as inversion phenomena (Fritts and Alexander, 2003; Lindzen, 1981; Smith, 2012). In addition, the gravity wave breaking influence on MLT dynamics is attempted to be demonstrated as the emergence of the inversion phenomenon over mid and high latitudes (Gan et al., 2012; Walterscheid and Hickey, 2009; Collins et al., 2011; Szewczyk et al., 2013). Observational and modeling approaches had been used to investigate GWs as the causative of an inversion (Fritts, 2018; Collins et al., 2014; Sridharan et al., 2008; Ramesh and Sridharan, 2012; Ramesh et al., 2013, 2014, 2017). The effect of gravity waves in the MLT inversion based on temperature variability is studied in particular over the mid and high-latitudes (Singh and Pallamraju, 2018;

[Fritts et al., 2018](#)). As a result, the inversion phenomenon has been the topic of numerous studies in MLT dynamics; yet, the mechanisms of development have been poorly understood.

Regarding over low-latitudes there are very less number of studies on the latitudinal/longitudinal variability of MLT inversion phenomenon associated with gravity wave activity provides motivation to investigate MLT inversion phenomenon and its association with gravity wave activity along with stability criteria using Brunt-Vaisala frequency (N^2) over low latitudinal band (3-15⁰N) using long term SABER observations during (2005-2020). The article is organized as follows: The data and method of extracting the MLT inversions phenomenon are presented in Section 5.2, and their results are described in Section 5.3, and finally Section 5.4 presents the conclusions.

5.2 Data and Analysis

SABER Observation data

The TIMED/SABER satellite provides the temperature profiles with good spatial and temporal resolution to investigate the MLT dynamics and their atmospheric wave processes ([Nath and Sridharan., 2014](#); [Gan et al., 2012](#); [Bizuneh et al., 2022](#); [Lingerew et al., 2023](#)). In the present study, the SABER vertical temperature profiles in the region of 60-100 km altitude during the period January 2005 to December 2020 over the low latitudes (3-15⁰N) are used to investigate the dynamics of the lower and upper MLT inversions phenomenon and their causatives. [Figure.5.1](#) illustrates the long-term mesosphere and lower thermosphere temperature variability in the height between 60 & 100 km over the low latitude 3-15⁰ N during the period 2005-2020 using the TIMED/SABER observation data. The monthly mean temperature shows maximum temperature (200–240 K) in the height range of 60–70 km, with the minimum temperature declining to around 160–180 K at a height range about 95–100 km.

Figure 5.1: The monthly mean MLT temperature variability in the height range of 60–100 km during December 2005–January 2020 over the low latitude.

Analysis technique

Mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) temperature inversions are identified based on their characteristics thickness and amplitude corresponding to altitude and temperature difference between the top and bottom levels (Leblanc and Hauchecorne, (1997); Fehine et al., (2008)). In this investigation the upper and lower MLT inversions are identified using the following criteria: (1) The bottom level of the lower and upper inversions is above 75 and 85 km, and its top level of inversion is below 87 and 92 km, respectively; (2) the amplitude is considered larger than 5 K; and (3) the thickness is greater than or equal to 2 km following the procedure. Inversions that satisfy the above-mentioned criteria are considered significant. This temperature inversion diagnostic techniques was applied to the daily SABER observation of 16 years of data from 2005–2020 over low latitudes.

The atmospheric stability is characterized based on Brunt-Vaisala frequency, which defined as:

$$N^2(z) = \frac{g(z)}{T_0(z)} \left(\frac{\partial T_0(z)}{\partial z} + \Gamma_d \right) \quad (5.1)$$

Where g is the acceleration due to gravity, N is the Vaisala frequency oscillation, T_0 is the background temperature, it is estimated based on the third-order polynomial fitting, $\Gamma_d = g/c_p$ is

the adiabatic lapse rate, and $c_p = 1004 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1}$ is the specific heat capacity of the atmosphere at constant pressure. When Vaisala frequency N^2 , is statically positive, the atmosphere is stable. Whereas the frequency N^2 , is negative, the atmosphere is unstable, in which the atmospheric lapse rate, $\Gamma = -\frac{\partial T}{\partial z}$ is larger than the adiabatic lapse rate, $\frac{g}{c_p} \approx 9.5 \text{ K km}^{-1}$, the atmosphere is unstable.

In order to identifying the impacts of atmospheric gravity waves on the atmospheric parameters, temperature profiles requires filtering. The third-order polynomial fit of the Least Squares has been applied to estimate the background temperature (T_0) from the observation following the procedure adapted by Ramesh & Sridharan, (2012). Hence, the temperature perturbations (T_p) are estimated by subtracting the background from the observational temperature data (T).

$$T_p = T - T_0 \quad (5.2)$$

This perturbed temperature, T_p is used to estimate the potential energy (E_p) (John and Kumar, 2012) to understand the atmospheric gravity waves. In this investigation, the cutoff frequency of the low-pass band filter of a 1-hour is used to remove the planetary wave and tidal wave contribution in order to extract short-period gravity wave. It is generally assumed that temperature profiles of the atmosphere are comprised of a background temperature on which there is an imposed fluctuating component. These temperature fluctuations are thus considered to be reflections of the wave activity at any given height.

$$E_p(z) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{g(z)}{N(z)} \right)^2 \left(\frac{T_p(z)}{T_0(z)} \right)^2 \quad (5.3)$$

These fluctuations are extracted and subjected to further analysis to estimate the potential energy of the waves as a function of altitude, z that quantify the wave activity of the region under study.

5.3 Results and Discussion

The daily SABER MLT temperature profiles for the period of 2005-2020 over low latitudes (3-15° N) is depicted in the form of contours in Figure 5.2(a and c). The daily inversion layers (MIL) occurrence in MLT temperature profiles are identified using the procedure mentioned in section 5.2 and corresponding contours drawn in the lower panels of Figure 5.2(b and d). The left side of upper panel of Figure 5.2(a) represents the daily upper MLT observed temperature variability is depicted in the range $\sim(180-205 \text{ K})$ at the height around $\sim 80-90 \text{ Km}$ and the right

upper panel of Figure 5.2(c) represents the lower MLT temperature variability at the range around $\sim(180-220\text{ K})$ in the height $\sim 70-80\text{ Km}$.

Whereas, the left side of the lower horizontal panel of Figure 5.2(b) represents the upper inversion layer of temperature around $\sim(180-220\text{ K})$ at upper MLT region around $\sim(80-90\text{ Km})$ is minimum compared to the right side of lower panel of Figure 5.2(d) of the lower inversion temperature in the range $\sim(180-225\text{ K})$ at lower MLT region in the height around $\sim(70-80\text{ Km})$, which refers the temperature gradient from negative to positive is observed due to external or internal drivers.

Figure 5.2: The upper and lower MLT observed temperatures in the first horizontal panel at (a & c) with their inversions in the second horizontal panel at (b & d)

The observed temperatures in the first horizontal panel, as indicated in Figure 5.2(a and c), have showed minimum values when compared to the SABER inversion temperatures in the second horizontal panel (Figure 5.2(b and d)). Our findings are similar with previous reports by Siva Kumar et al., (2001), which show that the base of the lower mesospheric inversion layer (MILs) lies in the range of 73-79 km, with a peak about 76 km. Similarly, Szewczyk et al. (2013) reported double mesospheric inversions at 71–73 km altitude with minimal amplitude compared to upper inversions at altitudes 86-89 km.

Figure 5.3: The frequency occurrence rate (percentage) of the (a) upper and (b) lower temperature inversions during 2005–2020 over low latitudes.

Further, the frequency occurrence (%) of mesospheric inversion layers (MILs) at upper and lower MLT region is investigated for the period of 2005-2020 and the results are displayed in the form of histogram in Figure 5.3(a) for upper MILs and in Figure 5.3(b) for lower MLT. The mean frequency occurrence rate of the upper inversion is approximately below 40% with the maximum rate of the upper inversion lies in between 60% and 78% particularly in the years 2008, 2010, and mid of 2016. While the mean frequency occurrence rate of the lower inversion is below 20%. In general, the occurrence rate of the upper inversion is relatively high compared with the lower inversion, which could be related to the atmospheric wave activities, particularly gravity wave activity is high in the upper MLT compared to the lower MLT atmospheric region (Hauchecorne et al., 1987; France et al., 2015).

Generally, the mesospheric inversion layer phenomenon is characterized by identifying inversion base height, inversion amplitude, and inversion thickness. The temperature and height differences between the inversion layers at the bottom and top are defined as the amplitude and thickness. The frequency of occurrence of amplitude, thickness, and base height of inversion are shown in the form of the histogram for upper and lower MILs in Figure 5.4(a-f) along with standard deviations (SD). In the left vertical column, three rows represent a histogram of (a) amplitude, (b) thickness, and (c) base of upper MILs phenomenon. The three rows of the right vertical column represents (d) amplitude (e) thickness, and (f) base of lower MILs phenomenon.

Figure 5.4: Histogram occurrence of MLT inversions. The first vertical panel represents the upper inversion distribution of (a) amplitude, (b) thickness, and (c) base, and the corresponding distribution in the second vertical panel is the lower inversion of (d) amplitude, (e) thickness, and (f) base over the low latitude during the period 2005–2020.

The upper inversion amplitude exists in the range between 20 and 80 K with a peak value of 38 K following Gaussian distribution with large standard deviations (SD) of 18.6 (Figure 5.4(a)). The thickness of the inversion layer for upper MILs has existed in the range of 3-9 K with the most probable value of 5.5 K with low standard deviations (SD) of 2.3 (Figure 5.4(b)). The base height of the upper MIL ranges from 77.5-90 km with a peak value of around 78 km showing less standard deviations (SD) of 2.8. Whereas, the lower inversion amplitude is depicted in the range between 10 and 60 K with a peak of 25 K with standard deviations (SD) of 14.5 (Figure 5.4(d)). The thickness of an inversion has appeared in the range of 3-8 Km with the most probable value of 3.8 Km with low standard deviations (SD) of 1.72 (Figure 5.4(e)). The base height of the lower inversion is in the range between 69 and 78 km with peak value around 73 km by showing less standard deviations (SD) of 2.07.

5.3.1 Latitudinal Variations of Mesospheric Inversion Layers (MIL)

In this section spatiotemporal (latitudinal-time) variability of MILs phenomenon and its characteristics such as amplitude, thickness and base has been investigated over low latitude band (3-15°N) during the period of 2005-2020 and the corresponding contour plots of latitude Vs. inversion amplitude in Figure 5.5(a), latitude Vs. thicknesses in Figure 5.5(b) and latitude Vs. base height in Figure 5.5(c) displayed. Upper MILs phenomenon is observed around ~80-90 km) with the maximum amplitude in the range of 90-120 K over all the latitude (5°-12° N) band particularly at 2005, 2007, mid of 2011, 2013, 2015, 2016, mid of 2019, and 2020. The inversion thickness depicted in the second horizontal shown in Figure 5.5(b) is displayed the maximum range of ~8-12 Km) over all latitudinal range 3-15°N. Figure 5.5(c) displays the relative maximum inversion base height around ~84-88 Km) in the latitudinal range between 4 and 14° N during 2006, 2008, 2010, 2012, 2016 and 2018.

Figure 5.5: The daily upper inversions (~80- 90 km) of (a) amplitude, (b) thickness, and (c) base height during 2005–2020 over latitudinal variation.

Similarly, the latitudinal variations of the lower inversion (MILs) phenomenon and their characteristics are depicted in the form of contour plots in Figure 5.6(a) for latitude Vs amplitude in Figure 5.6(b) for latitude Vs thickness and in Figure 5.6(c) for latitude Vs base height over the altitudinal range around $\sim(70-80$ km). The lower inversion amplitude is depicted in the range of $\sim 30-60$ k over all latitudinal bands except the maximum range of $\sim(80-100$ K) during 2013, 2015, 2016, and 2019 in different latitudinal values enclosed in the range between 5 and 14° N. Figure 5.6(b) displays the inversion thickness in the range of $(5-7$ km) over all latitude band except the maximum thickness presented in the range approximately $(8-10$ Km). The inversion of base height $(76-80)$ is depicted in Figure 5.6(c) over all latitudes except the period of 2008, 2014, and mid of 2018 with maximum base height.

From the Figures (5.5 & 5.6), it clearly observed that the upper inversion amplitude and thicknesses shown high values in comparison with lower inversion indicates of highly dynamical phenomenon over upper MLT region.

Figure 5.6: Same as figure 5.5, but for the lower MLT inversions ($\sim 70-80$ km)

5.3.2 Separations of the Perturbed Temperature in the MLT Region

This section deals the isolation of perturbed temperature profiles (T_p) at inversion days during the period of 2005-2020 in the upper and lower MLT regions can further required to calculate potential energy of gravity wave and Brunt-vaisala frequency (N^2). The procedure for calculating perturbation temperature (T_p) is mentioned in methodology part.

First, the daily upper inversion profiles are identified at upper MLT region for entire observation period of 2005-2020 and displayed in the form of contour in Figure 5.7(a). It is noted that inversion temperature is in the range of ~ 170 - 220 K with less detectable variability. Now the background temperature (T_0) is calculated by applying 3rd order polynomial fit on an inversion days and corresponding contour plot is drawn in Figure 5.7(b). The background temperature clearly displays identifiable periodic variability in the range of ~ 195 - 197 K around ~ 82 - 87 km. The contours of perturbed temperature profiles (T_p), i.e. difference between observed inversion temperature (T) and corresponding background temperature profiles (T_0) displays in the range of -25 to $+25$ K as shown in Figure 5.7(c).

Figure 5.7: The vertical panels are: (a) inversion based on an observation; (b) background temperature based on poly fit; (c) perturbations to the upper MLT atmospheric region; and the second vertical panel is comparisons.

Similar procedure has been applied on all inversion days to calculate perturbed temperature (T_p) during the period of 2005-2020 at lower MLT region and their corresponding contours has been displayed in Figure 5.8(a-c). The daily observed lower inversion temperature in Figure 5.8(a) depicted the range of ~ 170 – 220 K and corresponding background temperature of lower inversion in the range around ~ 195 – 210 K with the maximum temperature of, ~ 200 – 210 K over the height ~ 70 – 72 Km as shown in Figure 5.8(b). The perturbed temperatures presented in Figure 5.8(c) displays the range between -25 and 20 K. It is noted that, the upper MLT perturbed temperature is maximum compared to the lower MLT region may due to high dynamic phenomenon.

Figure 5.8: Same as figure 5.7, but for the lower MLT atmospheric region.

5.3.3 Effects of Gravity Waves on MLT Inversions and associated Instability

In this section an attempt has been made to investigate longitudinal variability of gravity wave contribution on mesospheric inversion (MILs) phenomenon through calculating potential energy and their instability based on Brunt-vaisala frequency (N^2) criteria. Since the previous section clearly reveals the perturbations of MLT temperature within the range of $\sim (-20$ to 20 K), hence, the low pass band filter corresponds to the cut-off frequency of one-hour on time series

temperature profile is applied to the period during 2005-2020 as depicted in Figure 5.9(a, b, c, & d) at selected heights of 90, 85, 75, and 70 km. The reason behind using the low pass band filter is to eliminate the influence of long period oscillations such as tidal or planetary waves of zonal wave. The effects of low pass filter is clearly visible before and after applying the filter in Figure 5.9(a & b) for upper MLT region at 90 and 85 km and in Figure 5.9(c & d) for lower MLT region at 75 and 70 km, the amplitude of the perturbed temperature is reduced to the range around $\sim(-10$ to 10 K) and data is smoothed by eliminating higher frequencies.

Figure 5.9: Perturbed temperature profiles before (red color) and after (blue color) applying the low pass band filter for upper (85 & 90 km) and lower (70 & 75 km) region.

By using the time series of filtered perturbed temperature data at selected heights of 90, 85, 75, and 70 km, the potential energy (E_p) is constructed based on the formula mentioned in the methodology section, since gravity wave activity is projected by potential energy calculation in numerous authors (Tsuda et al., 2000; Wang and Geller, 2003; Liu et al., 2014; Thurairajah et al., 2014). The spatiotemporal variability of gravity wave potential energy is shown in Figure 5.10(a & b) for upper MLT region at (90 & 85 km) and Figure 5.10(c & d) for lower MLT region at (75 and 70 km).

Figure 5.10: Gravity wave potential energy for upper (85 & 90 km) and lower (70 & 75 km) MLT region.

The maximum gravity wave potential energies in the range around $\sim 70-90$ J/kg is observed over the longitudinal regions of $45-47^{\circ}\text{E}$, 43°E & 44°E during 2011, 2017, & 2019 (Figure 5.10(a)) for upper MLT inversions at 90 km, whereas low potential energy around $\sim 10-60$ J/kg is presented in all over the longitudinal region from $33-48^{\circ}\text{E}$. While at 85 km shown in Figure 5.10(b) depicts the maximum potential energy around $\sim (70-100$ J/kg) over the longitudinal (34° , 44° , & 46°) regions during the period of 2014, 2016, & 2018. The low potential energy between 20 & 70 J/kg are appeared in all over the longitude ($33-48$) regions. The gravity wave potential energy is presented in Figure 5.10(c and d) for lower MLT region at 75 and 70 km. At the height 75 km, the maximum potential energy is appeared in the range 40-50 J/kg over the longitudinal (46° , 42° , 40° , 37° , 36° , & 38°) region during 2011, 2012, 2017, 2013-2015, 2018, & 2020. Similarly Figure 5.10(d) depicted the gravity wave potential energy in the range (2-30 J/kg) for the lower MLT region at 70 km over the longitudinal region ($33-48^{\circ}$). Out of which the maximum potential energy is found in the range between 25 & 30 J/kg in certain longitude region and time period. The result concludes that the observation of high potential energy at upper MLT region is due to deposition of high energy and momentum to the background temperature by gravity wave breaking could influence the dynamics of inversion phenomenon. The gravity wave dynamics are multi-scale in nature; small-scale waves might contribute

predominantly to instabilities, turbulence, and mixing (Liu and Meriwether, 2004; Szewczyk et al., 2013).

Hence, in this part an attempt has been made to investigate the gravity wave contribution on MIL phenomenon of unstable region based on the Brunt-Vaisala frequency calculations as mentioned in the methodology. The spatiotemporal variability of Vaisala frequency is displayed in the contours in Figure 5.11(a and b) for the upper MLT region (90 & 85 km) and in Figure 5.11(c and d) for the lower MLT region (75 and 70 km). Based on N^2 , the upper inversion instability is maximum at 90 km (~ 0.027) and at 85 km (~ 0.029) relative to the lower inversion instability at 75 km (~ 0.033) and 70 km (~ 0.035). This result leads us to the conclusion, a high amount of gravity wave potential energy is a consequence of high instability of upper inversion relative to the lower.

Figure 5.11: Brunt-viasal frequency (N^2) profiles for upper (85 & 90 km) and lower (70 & 75 km) MLT region.

5.3.4 Conclusions

In this article 16 years of SABER MLT temperature profiles are utilized to investigate MILs phenomenon and their causative mechanism through gravity wave potential energy (P_E) and instability criteria of Brunt-Vaisala frequency (N^2) over low latitude bands (3-15 $^{\circ}$ N). The observational conclusions from this chapter are drawn as follows:

- ✓ The frequency of occurrence on upper and lower MLT region reveals that, the mean occurrence rate for upper MLT inversions lies below 40% and for lower inversion below 20%.
- ✓ Based on the analysis of frequency of occurrence on mesospheric inversion layer (MIL) characteristic features reveals that the most probable value for upper inversion amplitude is 38 k with standard deviations (SD) of 1.72 K, inversion layer thicknesses is 5.5 Km with SD of 2.3 km and the base height of 78 Km with SD of 2.8 km. Whereas for lower inversion amplitude is 25 K with an SD of 14.5 K, the inversion layer thickness is 3.8 km with San D of 1.72 km and a base height of 73 with an SD of 2.07 km.
- ✓ The gravity wave indicator potential energy depicts high energy (below 100J/kg) at the upper MLT region (85 and 90 km) compared to the lower MLT region (75 and 70 km) with less than 50J/kg.
- ✓ The stability criteria at the MLT region is indicated by Brunt-Vaisala frequency (N^2), which shows low values at the upper MLT region (90 and 85 km) relative to the lower MLT region (75 and 70 km), leading to the conclusion that high potential energy at upper MLT region is due to the instability over that region gives rise to large inversion phenomenon.
- ✓ In general we concluded the processes in the atmosphere varies from region to region. As a result, the atmospheric state varies significantly with altitude as well as from place to place and time to time.

CHAPTER SIX

6. NN-MLT Model Prediction for Low-Latitude MLT Regions Based on Neural-Network and Long-term SABER Observation

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6.1 Introduction

The mesosphere and lower thermosphere (MLT) regions serve as a dynamic transition zone between the lower atmosphere, heavily influenced by anthropogenic and atmospheric wave activity, and the upper atmosphere, subject to significant solar activity and radiative forcing. The MLT region is characterized by several dynamic processes, particularly dynamic forcing due to atmospheric wave breaking (He et al., 2022; Jacobson, 2001; Jie et al., 2023; Kim and Achatz, 2021) and anthropogenic and radiative forcing (Beig, 2011; Beig et al., 2003). The dynamics of the equatorial MLT region differ considerably from those of mid- and high-latitude regions due to the presence of both natural and anthropogenic influences. Currently, MLT variability is being studied both regionally and globally (Ji et al., 2022; Vincent, 2015). In this context, satellite-based observational studies of the MLT region are essential and have been employed in numerous research initiatives. The HALOE/UARS satellite provides temperature profiles of the upper atmosphere between 35 and 86 km (Remsberg, 2002), while the Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS) offers global temperature observations between 20 and 90 km (Wu et al., 2003). The satellite, equipped with Broadband Emission Radiometry (SABER)/Thermosphere, Ionosphere, and Mesosphere Energetics and Dynamics (TIMED) satellite provides global temperature profiles with good vertical resolution, aiding in investigating the natural influences on the MLT region (Bizuneh et al., 2022; Gan et al., 2012, 2014, 2017; Nath & Sridharan, 2014; Xu et al., 2007). However, one significant limitation of the MLT region is the lack of continuous and reliable measurements, leading to its colloquial nickname, “ignosphere.” This lack makes continuous monitoring of mesospheric and lower thermosphere dynamics difficult. Despite these challenges, a comprehensive understanding of the MLT characteristics is essential for developing

an efficient model that effectively bridges the gap between satellite and ground-based observations.

MLT models serve as essential tools for the upper atmospheric research community. Therefore, various scientific and operational models have been developed to understand the dynamics of MLT variability, including the Jacchia series model, the drag temperature model (DTM), and the mass spectrometric inhomogeneous scattering (MSIS) model (Hedin, 1987, 1991; Hedin et al., 1977; Reber and Hays, 1973). The Jacchia-71 model, later updated to CIRA-72, is an empirical model that has been used to measure the temperature and density of the MLT region since the early 1960s. The Jacchia 70 and Jacchia 71 models underpin NASA's Marshall Engineering Thermosphere (MET). Since the early 1970s, Alan Hedin and others have created a new density model called MSIS, which is a popular choice for atmospheric modeling in the scientific community. Various researchers have employed the MSIS family of models (MSISE-86, MSISE-90, NRLMSISE-00, and NRLMSISE-2.0), Jacchia 70, and DTM models in their respective studies (Bruinsma, 2015; Emmert et al., 2020; Hedin, 1987, 1991; Jacchia, 1970; Picone et al., 2002). A family of MSIS empirical models has been developed and refined to describe the atmospheric temperature, number density, and mass density of eight species spanning from the ground to the exosphere (Hedin, 1991). The updated Naval Research Laboratory (NRLMSISE-00) empirical atmospheric model suffers from inherent limitations in satellite information for determining the composition and structure of the MLT atmosphere, particularly below 100 km (Picone et al., 2002). The NRLMSIS2-0 empirical model, an upgrade from the earlier version, NRLMSISE-00, has become the most recent and popular version of MSIS (Emmert et al., 2020). This model extends from the ground to the exosphere, characterizing the mean observed patterns of temperature and eight species densities.

Artificial neural network-based models have recently drawn the attention of the research community across various disciplines due to their capacity to capture nonlinear relationships between inputs and outputs. Predictive models based on neural networks (NN) can often outperform traditional physical and statistical methods (Tran et al., 2021). The NN toolbox, readily available in popular machine learning programming environments such as Matlab and Python (Demuth et al., 2006; Loh, 2005), allows for quick analysis of NN-based models. At present, the NN-based modeling technique serves as an alternative approach to predicting atmospheric variability dynamics. Due to the scarcity of long-term data, no significant results

have been reported on equatorial MLT variability using the NN technique. This research concentrates on developing NN model and predicting low-latitude (3° - 15° N) MLT temperature variability based on long-term SABER observations. Additionally, the performance of the proposed NN-based model is evaluated using SABER observational data and compared to the NRLMSISE2-0 empirical model. The article is structured as follows: Section 6.2 is outline the data and methodology, including an explanation of the NN architecture. A description and discussion of the results follow in Section 6.3, 6.4, 6.5 & 6.6 while Section 6.7 presents the conclusions.

6.2 Data and Method

Data descriptions

The TIMED/SABER, provides atmospheric temperature and ozone constituent measurements, including the region 60–100 km above the ground, with a 1 km spatial resolution and a 1-hr temporal resolution (Bizuneh et al., 2022). Data used in the development of the neural network-based NN-MLT model includes TIMED/SABER observations and the NRLMSIS2-0 model. The NRLMSIS2-0 empirical model data, a substantial revision of the earlier NRLMSISE-00 version, covers the Earth to the exosphere, capturing the mean observed patterns of temperature, eight types of densities, and air mass density. The NRLMSIS2-0 model is selected to evaluate and validate the performance of the neural network based NN-MLT model. In the training process to develop the neural network (NN) based NN-MLT model, five known input variables data, such as universal time (UT), latitude, longitude, F10.7 solar flux, and ozone volume mixing ratio, are used in addition to SABER temperature and ozone data for prediction as mentioned in chapter 3 with data sources in detail.

Neural-Network training:

A total of fifteen years of SABER observation data (from 2006 to 2020) is utilized and split into two datasets for training and testing the neural network-based model. In this analysis, the training dataset comprises approximately 90% of the total observation data from January 01, 2006, to December 31, 2019, while the remaining 10% of data from January 01, 2020, to December 31, 2020, is employed for testing. After developing the model through network training, it can be evaluated, and predictions can be made using the testing dataset. The testing dataset is independent and not used during training but serves to assess the network model's predictive

performance using various statistical techniques. These techniques include mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), standard deviation (σ), and correlation coefficient (R) analysis. Different scholars widely use these methods (Oliveira et al., 2023; Santos et al., 2023; Martins et al., 2013; Habarulema et al., 2007; Leandro and Santos, 2007) to measure the performance of network models. The readers are suggested to refer in chapter 3 section 3.4.4 for complete technical details of NN-Architecture.

6.3 Result and discussion

6.3.1 Performance of neural network based NN-MLT model prediction in MLT

In this section, a neural network-based NN-MLT model was developed for low latitudes (3-15°N) in the MLT region at three different altitude levels, using the methodology described in Section 3.2. The model was trained with 90% of the observed data from a total of 15 years of observations between January 2006 and December 2020, while the remaining 10% of data from January 2020 to December 2020 was used to test the performance of the NN-MLT model prediction. The aim was to evaluate the accuracy and predictability of the NN-MLT model. In addition to evaluating the 90(10) trained-based model of NN-MLT predictability, two other partition options, 80(20) and 70(30), were used to determine which provided better performance. Based on the statistical metrics (Pearson's correlation coefficient, standard deviation, and root mean square errors), as shown in Figure 6.1, the NN-MLT model exhibits high performance in the 90(10) partition compared to the 80(20) and 70(30) partitions. After the successful execution of the 90(10) NN-MLT model, the predicted output values at three altitude levels were compared with the SABER observed values. The prediction capability's performance was evaluated using the statistical metrics of Pearson's correlation coefficient and error distribution in Figure 6.1 for each partition at three altitude levels. The left side of the vertical panels (Figures 6.1a, b & c) displays a scatter plot between the SABER observed temperature and the NN-MLT model predictions, along with the best fit linear regression indicated by red lines and the correlation (R) values specified on each figure. On the other hand, the right-side vertical panels of Figures (6.1d, e & f) show the error distributions of the NN-MLT model forecast compared to SABER observations with σ , and RMSE.

Figure 6.1: The first vertical panels (a, b, and c) represent the comparisons of scatter plots between NN-MLT model predictions and observed values, along with the best-fit linear regression red lines for the 90(10), 80(20), and 70(30) partitions of the model, respectively. The second corresponding vertical panels (d, e, and f) indicate the error distributions of the NN-MLT model for each partition.

Histograms illustrating the hourly, temporal frequency distributions of a one-year residual temperature between the observations and the NN-MLT model in the MLT region are shown in Figures (6.1d, e & f) at different altitudes. The residual temperature (error) distribution is approximately Gaussian at all altitudes, indicating a normal distribution. The width of the distribution remains relatively constant at 60 km for all partitions (90(10), 80(20), and 70(30)) with a standard deviation ranging between 4.18 and 4.30 K. However, at 75 km for all partitions, the width of the residual temperature distributions is relatively higher, with a standard deviation ranging between 8.89 and 9.64 K. This pattern is similar at 90 km for all partitions, with a range between 12.38 and 12.71 K. Table 6.1 presents the detailed error metric (R , R^2 , σ , and RMSE) values at three different heights for each of three partition datasets used to train the model.

The three 90(10), 80(20), and 70(30) partitions of the model are presented in Figure 6.1, and all partitions of the model at 60 km show better performance compared to 75 and 90 km, with the 90(10)-partition data of the NN-MLT model prediction performing the best. The strong performance of the model is well described by a high R and a small RMSE. Table 1 clearly displays a high R value of 0.74 and a smaller RMSE of 4.35 K at 60 km altitude, capturing the 90(10)-partition model's superior performance compared to the other two partitions, 80(20) and 70(30). Therefore, the NN-MLT model prediction's 90(10) train-test partition correlates well with the SABER observed values. The other two partitions, 80(20) and 70(30), are also presented to evaluate the performance of the 90(10)-partition based on the NN-MLT model. Henceforth, the analysis will continue with the model's 90(10) partition data. The 90(10) partition of the model performs well at 60 km (74%), 75 km (73%), and 90 km (72%).

Table 6.1 Pearson's correlation coefficient (R), coefficient of determination (R^2), standard deviation (σ), and root mean square error (RMSE) of statistical distributions for the 90(10), 80(20), and 70(30) partitions of the predictions.

Height (H)	Correlation coefficient (R)			Coefficient of determination (R^2)			Standard deviation (σ) in K			Root mean square error (RMSE) in K		
	90/10	80/20	70/30	90/10	80/20	70/30	90/10	80/20	70/30	90/10	80/20	70/30
60 km	0.74	0.73	0.72	0.54	0.54	0.52	4.30	4.27	4.18	4.35	5.43	4.23
75 km	0.68	0.65	0.65	0.46	0.42	0.43	8.89	9.53	9.64	8.89	9.68	9.88
90 km	0.65	0.67	0.66	0.44	0.45	0.42	12.83	12.38	12.71	12.83	12.39	13.06

6.3.2 Evaluation of the NN-MLT Model in Predicting the Spatiotemporal distribution of MLT Temperature

The TIMED/SABER observations provide realistic information about the spatial (e.g., latitude, longitude, and elevation) and temporal (e.g., monthly, seasonal, and short-term) distributions of the MLT temperature variability. Thus, the spatiotemporal temperature variations of the MLT have been investigated with the NN-MLT model. Figures (6.2 & 6.3) show the spatial and temporal contours of temperature variability using both the NN-MLT model and SABER observations over low latitude ($3-15^{\circ}$ N) in the MLT region over a one-year period from January to December 2020.

Figure 6.2: The longitude vs. latitude variations of MLT temperature variability derived from (a) the NN-MLT model, (b) SABER observations, and (c) the percentage errors at 60, 75, and 90 km altitudes.

The vertical panels of Figures (6.2a, 6.2b, & 6.2c) display the geographical longitude versus latitude variations of temperature in the mesosphere and lower thermosphere regions at selected 60, 75, and 90 km altitudes. The NN-MLT-derived model in Figure (6.2a) is presented in the first vertical panel and compared to the SABER observations in Figure (6.2b) within the middle vertical panel. The error (residual) distributions between them are shown in the third vertical panel of Figure (6.2c). The temperature variations predicted by the NN-MLT model correspond closely with the SABER observations, indicating that the NN-MLT model effectively captures the spatial temperature variations at 60 km compared to those at 75 and 90 km altitude, as demonstrated in the first horizontal panel of Figure (6.2a) with the minimum error (Figure 6.2c). The percentage error is calculated using the following expression:

$$\text{Percentage of error (\% Err)} = \frac{\text{NN-MLT model} - \text{SABER observation}}{\text{SABER observation}} \times 100 \quad (6.4)$$

The percentage errors can be observed from the third vertical panel of Figure (6.2c), which displays the three altitudes of 60, 75, and 90 km. At the 60 km altitudinal level of temperature, the percentage error remains below 10%. This indicates that the NN-MLT model effectively captures the spatial variation of temperature. However, the NN-MLT model prediction appears to overestimate the SABER observations at an altitude of 75 km, as the error increases to about 20%, while at 90 km, the NN-MLT model underestimates the observational data by a factor of more than 18%.

The analysis now proceeds to examine the temporal variability of temperature by latitude and universal time at three altitude levels in the mesosphere and the lower thermosphere region by examining universal time versus latitude from the NN-MLT model and SABER observations. Figures (6.3a–6.3c) display contours of universal time versus latitudinal variations of temperature using the NN-MLT model in Figure (6.3a), presented in the first vertical panel, the SABER observations in Figure (6.3b) in the second vertical panel, and the error distribution in Figure (6.3c) in the last vertical panel. It is clear that the predicted temperature fluctuations in the NN-MLT model are highly correlated with the SABER observations. The error distribution of the temperature variability, predicted by the model and observed at all altitudinal levels, is in the range between 5 and 20%. The minimum and maximum percentage errors exist at different altitudinal regions throughout the entire period of time. This indicates that the NN-MLT model prediction overestimates the SABER observations at all altitude levels (60, 75, and 90 km).

Figure 6.3: Time vs. latitude variations of MLT temperature derived from (a) NN-MLT, (b) SABER observations, and (c) the percentage errors at 60, 75, and 90 km altitudes.

6.3.3 Seasonal Variations of NN-MLT Model and SABER observations

In this section, the seasonal variations of MLT temperatures from the NN-MLT model and SABER observations at three MLT height levels are examined. The upper horizontal panel of Figure (6.4) displays the mesosphere and lower thermosphere temperatures in longitude-latitude variations during the equinoxes (March and September) and solstices (June and December) of the SABER observations at 60 km altitude. The bottom horizontal panel of Figure (6.4) presents the predicted temperature variability from the NN-MLT model. Similarly, Figures (6.5 & 6.6) show the spatial variations of MLT temperature at 75 and 90 km heights, respectively.

Figure 6.4: MLT temperature maps generated at a height of 60 km from the NN-MLT model and SABER observations during the 2020 June/December solstice and March/September equinox.

Figure (6.4) clearly shows that the equinox period exhibits a maximum temperature of 240 K at latitude (4–12) and longitude (34–46) bands of both the NN-MLT model and SABER observations, except for March. In contrast, the solstice season shows minimum temperatures of 230 K at all latitude and longitude bands, while its maximum value, except for the June solstice, is about 250 K in both the model and SABER observations. During the September equinox, a maximum temperature of approximately 205 K is observed at latitude (4–12)⁰ and longitude (34–46)⁰ bands from both the NN-MLT model and SABER observations at 75 km altitude (Figure 6.5). Instead, alternating maximum and minimum temperature bands are observed during the solstice, based on both the model and observations.

Even during the equinox, only March exhibits a maximum temperature of 210 K based on both the model and SABER observations at 90 km (Figure 6.6). In contrast, September displays a minimum temperature of 150 K from both SABER observations and the NN-MLT model in all

longitude-latitude bands, except for some specific longitude-latitude bands [i.e., long (44^0) vs. lat (4^0-8^0); long (35^0) vs. lat (4^0-6^0); and long (43^0) vs. lat (10^0-12^0)].

Figure 6.5: MLT temperature maps generated at a height of 75 km from the NN-MLT model and SABER observations during the 2020 June/December solstice and March/September equinox.

As usual, alternating bands of maximum and minimum temperatures are observed during the solstice. It can be concluded that during the equinoxes, especially in March, the maximum temperature in the MLT region is visible at three altitude levels across all latitudes and longitudes. In contrast, the solstice months display alternating bands of maximum and minimum temperatures at different latitudes and longitudes. Furthermore, it was found that the simulation magnitude of the NN-MLT model temperature is typically smaller than the SABER observations by 2–5 K at 60 km, 1–7 K at 75 km, and by a maximum of 5–15 K at 90 km. A substantial deviation like this might be due to the evaluation of SABER temperature measurement inaccuracies at these altitudes (Remsberg et al., 2008). Thus, the result implies that the NN-MLT model prediction demonstrates a strong capability to describe atmospheric temperatures in the MLT region.

Figure 6.6: MLT temperature maps generated at a height of 90 km from the NN-MLT model and SABER observations during the 2020 June/December solstice and March/September equinox.

6.3.4 Comparisons of NN-MLT and NRLMSIS2.0 Model Predictions with SABER Observations

In this section, the performance of the NN-MLT model is compared and evaluated alongside the standard empirical NRLMSIS2-0 model, using SABER observational data for reference. The first set of vertical panels' presents comparison of MLT temperature variations as observed by SABER, predicted by the NN-MLT model, and estimated by the NRLMSISE2-0 empirical model at altitudinal levels of 60, 75, and 90 km during the Equinox and Solstice seasons. The second and third sets of vertical panels show histogram hourly distributions of the residual temperature differences between SABER observations and predictions by both models, NN-MLT and NRLMSISE2-0, as depicted in Figures (6.7, 6.8 & 6.9).

Figure 6.7: Comparisons of MLT temperature variations at 60 km during the Equinox and Solstice periods. SABER data is represented by black circles, the empirical NRLMSISE2-0 model by blue circles, and the NN-MLT model by red circles in the first vertical panel. The second and third vertical panels display the histograms of hourly distributions of the residual temperature between the SABER observations and the two models, NN-MLT and NRLMSISE2-0.

An attempt was made to plot the NN-MLT model's short-term (hourly) temperature forecasts at the three MLT altitudinal levels for the solstices and equinoxes, as shown in the first vertical panel of Figures (6.7a, 6.8a & 6.8a). The figure is superimposed with SABER observations and NRLMSIS2.0 empirical model values. These results clearly demonstrate the model's ability to simulate MLT temperatures effectively. Compared to the NRLMSISE2-0 empirical model, the NN-MLT model provides smoother variations that appear to outperform the empirical model. The statistical controls of the NN-LMT and NRLMSIS2-0 models are summarized using the same approaches as for NRLMSIS.00 (Picone et al., 2002) with the following error distributions:

mean (μ) including bias and standard deviation (σ). Bias represents the systematic discrepancies between the observed data and the respective model estimates, while standard deviation signifies the variations between the observed data and the model (including measurement noise). By applying these error metrics to both the NN-MLT model and the standard NRLMSIS2-0 empirical models at the three MLT height levels, the results are shown as histograms in Figures (6.7b, 6.8b, & 6.9b) for the NN-MLT model placed in the second vertical panel and Figures (6.7c, 6.8c & 6.9c) for the NRLMSIS2-0 empirical model placed in the third vertical panel.

Figure 6.8: Comparisons of MLT temperature variations at 75 km during the Equinox and Solstice periods. SABER data is represented by black circles, the empirical NRLMSISE2-0 model by blue circles, and the NN-MLT model by red circles in the first vertical panel. The second and third vertical panels display the histograms of hourly distributions of the residual temperature between the SABER observations and the two models, NN-MLT and NRLMSISE2-0.

The error distribution of the NRLMSIS 2.0 empirical model at 60 km is more concentrated at the solstice than the equinox, indicating that the model accurately describes the equinox temperature changes. The error distribution is similar to that of the SABER observations at 60 km, although, at 90 km, it coincides more with the solstice than the equinoxes. However, this empirical model simulation is well captured at a height of 75 km during both the September equinox and June solstice. The NRLMSIS 2.0 standard deviations range from 14.94 to 17.37 K at 90 km, 11.29 to 15.69 K at 75 km, and 5.15 to 6.92 K at 60 km. The standard deviation of the NN-MLT model is also in the range of 11.59-13.53 K for 90 km, 7.52-10.92 K for 75 km, and 2.97-4.67 K for 60 km. At all altitude levels, the standard deviations are smaller in the NN-MLT model, indicating that the model is more robust in capturing temperature fluctuations than the empirical NRLMSISE2.0 model.

Figure 6.9: Comparisons of MLT temperature variations at 90 km during the Equinox and Solstice periods. SABER data is denoted by black circles, the empirical NRLMSISE2-0 model by blue circles, and the NN-MLT model by red circles in the first vertical panel. The second and third vertical panels display histograms of hourly distributions of the residual temperature between the SABER observations and the two models, NN-MLT and NRLMSISE2-0.

The standard deviations of the NN-MLT and NRLMSIS2-0 models over the upper MLT region were at their maximum during the equinox, while their minimum standard deviations were at the solstice at heights of 75 and 90 km. In contrast, they are reversed in the lower MLT region at 60 km, with a maximum at the solstice and a minimum at the equinox. The NN-MLT model standard deviations are typically in the range 2-2.56 K lower than the empirical model NRLMSIS2-0 and 0.4-3.34 K and 3.18-4.6 K in the upper MLT at 75 and 90 km throughout the equinox and solstice seasons. For all regions of the MLT at 60, 75, and 90 km during all equinox and solstice seasons, the residual standard deviation of the observed MLT temperature is smaller than that of the empirical NRLMSIS2-0 model. One may infer that the NN-MLT model is effectively fitted to the NRLMSIS 2.0 empirical model and SABER observations.

6.3.5 Summary and Conclusions

Few middle and upper atmosphere models were available to investigate the MLT dynamics variability, resulting in the development of the NN-MLT model in this work. Recently, NN-based models have attracted the research community's attention due to their ability to capture nonlinearity and produce more reliable performance than physical and statistical approaches. This chapter develops the NN-MLT model and analyzes its prediction over low latitudes ($3-15^{\circ}$ N); it is designed separately for specific altitudes of 60, 75, and 90 km using 14 years of data from 2006 to 2019 out of 15 years (2006 to 2020) of SABER observations, with the remaining one-year data used for validation and forecasting. The model development was explored with three data training and testing options, viz., 90(10), 80(20), and 70(30), of which the 90(10) data partition was found to be the best, so further analysis proceeded with this partition. The model's performance and its error metrics were analyzed, leading to several key conclusions: The NN-MLT model exhibits a high R-value and a small RMSE, indicating a good fit between the model and the observations, especially at 60 km altitude. However, at other altitudes, the model's forecast either overestimates (at 75 km altitude) or underestimates (at 90 km altitude) the SABER observations, leading to errors ranging from 12% to 20%. The model effectively captures spatial variability (longitude vs. latitude) at this altitude.

The seasonal variations (equinox and solstice) of the MLT temperature are investigated using the NN-MLT model and observations. During the equinoxes, especially in September, the MLT region exhibits maximum temperatures at all latitudes ($4-14^{\circ}$ N) and longitudes ($32-47^{\circ}$ E)

bands at three altitude levels. In contrast, the solstice months show alternating maximum and minimum temperatures at varying latitudes and longitudes. The forecasting ability of the NN-MLT model is further evaluated using the standard empirical model, NRLMSIS2-0. At an altitude of 60 km, the model captures equinox temperature fluctuations, while at an altitude of 75 km, it captures Sep-equinox and Jun-solstice temperature fluctuations. At 90 km altitude, it captures more of the solstice temperature fluctuations than the equinox. Considering these results, the dynamics require further investigation, linking them to the mesospheric temperature inversion phenomenon often occurring during equinoxes and solstices and even to gravity or tidal interactions. Note that NRLMSIS2-0 is an empirical model, while NN-MLT is based on satellite observations; it has large measurement errors in the upper mesospheric levels, which can cause differences between the two and require further analysis. Based on the analysis, it can be reasonably concluded that the NN-MLT model outperforms the NRLMSIS2-0 empirical model and aligns well with SABER observations in predicting MLT temperature variations at low latitudes.

CHAPTER SEVEN

7. Conclusions and Recommendations for Future Work

7.1 Conclusions of the study

The dissertation investigates the Mesosphere-Lower-Thermosphere (MLT) dynamics and their variability in three ways. The first motive of the problem, "Long-term temperature and ozone variability and its response to natural drivers in the MLT region using 16 years (2005-2020) of TIMED/SABER observation data over low-latitude (3-150N)," has been investigated, and the results are as follows:

- ✓ The dominant seasonal (AO and SAO) and long-term oscillations (QBO and ENSO and SC) are identified from the MLT temperature and ozone variability by applying wavelet technique.
- ✓ The seasonal oscillations AO and SAO are dominant in all MLT altitudinal levels (60–100 km) except at certain heights. Whereas, the long-term oscillations (QBO and ENSO) signatures are present at all heights with varying amplitudes during the entire study period, especially QBO possesses weak amplitudes at the upper MLT (80-100 km) region.
- ✓ The temperature and ozone responses to F10.7 are opposite to each other and vice-versa at the lower (60, 70, and 80 km) and upper (80, 90, and 100 km) MLT regions. F10.7 solar flux influences the upper MLT positively by the extents of (2.8 K and 0.7 ppmv) and negatively to the lower region (-2.0 K and 0.45 ppmv) in both temperature and ozone variability. At 80 km, the temperature and ozone respond in phase to all natural influences (F10.7, ENSO, and QBO), and are out of phase below and above 80 km.
- ✓ At all heights, the magnitude of the temperature response is greater than that of ozone. Finally, the MLT long-term temperature shows a cooling trend of -0.85 K/decade with an ozone composition value of -0.12 ppmv/decade in the lower MLT region (60-80 km), followed by a warming trend of 1.25 K/decade in temperature and 0.27 ppmv/decade in the upper MLT region (85-100 km).

The second goal of the topic, "The role of gravity waves in the mesosphere-lower-thermosphere (MLT) inversions over low latitude (3-15°N)," was explored in chapter 5, which is part of the dissertation, and the conclusions are as follows:

- ✓ The frequency of occurrence of MIL phenomenon at upper and lower MLT region reveals that, the mean occurrence rate for upper MLT inversions lies below 40% and for lower inversion below 20%.
- ✓ Based on the analysis of frequency of occurrence on mesospheric inversion layer (MIL) characteristic features reveals that the most probable values for upper inversion amplitude is 38 k with standard deviations (SD) of 1.72 k, inversion layer thicknesses is 5.5 Km with SD of 2.3 km and the base height of 78 Km with SD of 2.8 km. Whereas for lower inversion amplitude is 25 K with SD of 14.5 k, inversion layer thicknesses is 3.8 km with SD of 1.72 km and the base height of 73 with SD of 2.07 km.
- ✓ The gravity wave indicator potential energy depicts high energy (below 100J/kg) at upper MLT region (90 and 85 km) compared to lower MLT region (75 and 70 km) with less than 50J/kg.
- ✓ The stability criteria at MLT region is indicated by Brunt-Vaisala frequency (N^2), which shows low values at upper MLT region (90 and 85 km) relative to the lower MLT region (75 and 70 km), leads to the conclusion that high potential energy at upper MLT region is due to the instability over that region gives rise to large inversion phenomenon.

The third and last motive presented in chapter 6: Neural network based NN-MLT model over the low latitude is developed and prediction has been carried out using the long terms SABER observations and the concluded results are as follow:

- ✓ The model development was explored with three data training and testing options, via 90(10), 80(20), and 70(30), of which the 90(10) data partition was found to be the best, so further analysis proceeded with this partition.
- ✓ The NN-MLT model exhibits a high R-value and a small RMSE, indicating a good fit between the model and the observations, especially at 60 km altitude. The model effectively captures spatial variability (longitude vs. latitude) at this altitude. However, at other altitudes, the model's prediction either overestimates (at 75 km altitude) or underestimates (at 90 km altitude) the observations, leading to errors ranging from 12% to 20%.
- ✓ The seasonal variations of the MLT temperature during the equinoxes, especially in September, the MLT region exhibits maximum temperatures at all latitudes (4^0N-14^0N) and

longitudes (32°E – 47°E) bands at three altitude levels. In contrast, the solstice months show alternating maximum and minimum temperatures at varying latitudes and longitudes.

- ✓ The forecasting ability of the NN-MLT model is further evaluated using the standard empirical model, NRLMSIS2-0. At 60 km altitude, the model captures equinox temperature fluctuations, while at an altitude of 75 km, it captures Sep-equinox and Jun-solstice temperature fluctuations. Whereas at 90 km altitude, it captures more of the solstice temperature fluctuations than the equinox.
- ✓ Final conclusion are drawn that the NN-MLT model outperforms the NRLMSIS2-0 empirical model and aligns well with SABER observations in predicting MLT temperature variations at low latitudes.

7.2 Recommendations for Future Work

In this section, recommendations for future work are presented based on the dissertation findings. While investigating the causative mechanism of the MIL phenomenon, we consider only gravity wave contribution; however, literature reviews suggest that additional waves such as tidal wave or planetary wave contribution should be investigated in the future. Whereas developing NN-MLT model we consider only five input parameters due to time constraints. The NN-MLT model based on SABER satellite observations has errors in the upper levels of the MLT that require further investigation. As a result, we suggest that future research consider including more influential parameters to improve model prediction performance and reduce errors in the upper and lower MLT regions above the equator.

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